

**Felipe
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**Ilustração vetorial aplicada a taxonomia de peixes
mesopelágicos
Vectorial scientific illustration – a graphic tool
applied to mesopelagic fishes taxonomy**

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Dissertação apresentada à Universidade de Aveiro para cumprimento dos requisitos necessários à obtenção do grau de Mestre em Biologia Aplicada, realizada sob a orientação científica do professor assistente Fernando Jorge S. Correia, Diretor do Laboratório de Ilustração Científica do Departamento de Biologia da Universidade de Aveiro

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Aos meus pais que me derão todo apoio e sem eles nada seria possível.

E aos amigos que sempre me ajudaram nessa jornada.

Resumo

A Ilustração vetorial possui inúmeras vantagens: as dimensões são independentes da resolução (escalonáveis), continuamente editáveis e programáveis. O estudo visa criar ilustrações vetoriais (Adobe Illustrator), com capacidade de edição adaptativa, aplicadas ao estudo da taxonomia. As principais estruturas diagnósticas para identificação dos peixes (fotóforos, nadadeiras e linha lateral), constituirão um inventário na pasta de símbolos, recorrendo à ferramenta Blend tool para criar padrões editáveis. As espécies modelo (arquétipos) utilizadas neste estudo foram os peixes mesopelágicos das famílias Myctophidae e Sternoptychidae, dado desempenharem um papel importante na cadeia trófica, conectando zooplâncton a predadores de topo. Apesar de serem extremamente abundantes e diversificados, são notórios os poucos guias que auxiliem na sua identificação. Neste projeto propomos a criação de um guia ilustrado para estas famílias, onde estruturas que compõem as espécies seriam disponibilizadas na forma de inventário de símbolos, permitindo a construção de novos arquétipos representativos de novas espécies e a sua adição ao guia, por outros ilustradores ou técnicos, conforme vão sendo descritas e/ou referenciadas a sua ocorrência.

Palavras-Chaves

Ilustração vetorial, vetores, taxonomia, peixes mesopelágicos, espécies-arquétipo

Abstract

Vectorial illustration has great advantages, since it is not resolution dependent, being always available to edition and programmable. This study aims to create vectorial illustrations (In Adobe Illustrator), with capacity to be edit and adapted to taxonomical studies. The major structures for fish identification (photophores, finrays and lateral line), will be programmed with the Blend tool and further deposit in a symbol inventory to create editable patterns. The species used in this study were mesopelagic fishes from the families Myctophidae and Sternoptychidae, being this families important in trophic chain, connecting the zooplankton to top predators. Even being very abundant and with a high biodiversity, few identification guides are available. In this study we create a guide for this species, using the vector libraries, leaving also this libraries available for other researchers to complement with new species as more campaigns are made and new species identified.

Key words

Vectorial illustration, vectors, taxonomy, mesopelagic fishes, archetype species

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Scientific illustration	1
1.2	Taxonomy and biological diversity	3
1.3	The deep sea	5
1.4	Seamounts	6
1.5	Family Myctophidae	7
1.6	Family Sternoptychidae	7
1.7	Why apply scientific illustration?	8
2	Material and methods	11
2.1	Sampling and identification of species	11
2.2	Collecting information	11
2.3	Adobe Illustrator	12
2.3.1	Artboard size	12
2.3.2	Pen tool	12
2.3.3	Pattern brush	14
2.3.4	Graphic style	14
2.3.5	Blend tool	15
2.3.6	Symbols	15
3	Results	17
3.1	Vector symbols	17
3.2	Family Myctophidae	18
3.2.1	Genus <i>Benthoosema</i>	19
3.2.2	Genus <i>Bolinichthys</i>	19
3.2.3	Genus <i>Ceratoscopelus</i>	20
3.2.4	Genus <i>Diaphus</i>	21
3.2.5	Genus <i>Diogenichthys</i>	22
3.2.6	Genus <i>Hygophum</i>	23
3.2.7	Genus <i>Lampadena</i>	24
3.2.8	Genus <i>Lampanyctus</i>	25
3.2.9	Genus <i>Lepidophanes</i>	26
3.2.10	Genus <i>Lobianchia</i>	27
3.2.11	Genus <i>Nannobrachium</i>	28
3.3	Family Sternoptychidae	31
3.3.1	Genus <i>Argyropelecus</i>	31
3.3.2	Genus <i>Polyipnus</i>	34
3.3.3	Genus <i>Sternoptyx</i>	35
3.3.4	Genus <i>Maurolicus</i>	36
3.3.5	Genus <i>Valenciennellus</i>	37
4	Discussion	39

5	References	43
I	Identification keys	49
I.1	Key to the Cape Verde genera of Myctophidae	49
I.1.1	<i>Benthoosema</i> Goode & Bean, 1896	60
I.1.2	<i>Bolinichthys</i> Paxton, 1972	60
I.1.3	<i>Centrobranchus</i> Fowler, 1904	62
I.1.4	<i>Ceratoscopelus</i> Günther, 1864	62
I.1.5	<i>Diaphus</i> Eigenmann & Eigenmann, 1890	63
I.1.6	<i>Diogenichthys</i> Bolin, 1939	76
I.1.7	<i>Electrona</i> Goode & Bean, 1896	76
I.1.8	<i>Gonichthys</i> Gistel, 1850	76
I.1.9	<i>Hygophum</i> Bolin, 1939	77
I.1.10	<i>Lampadena</i> Goode & Bean, 1896	79
I.1.11	<i>Lampanyctus</i> Bonaparte, 1840	82
I.1.12	<i>Lepidophanes</i> Fraser-Brunner, 1949	86
I.1.13	<i>Lobianchia</i> Gatti, 1903	87
I.1.14	<i>Loweina</i> Fowler, 1925	87
I.1.15	<i>Myctophum</i> Rafinesque, 1810	88
I.1.16	<i>Nannobrachium</i> Günther, 1887	91
I.1.17	<i>Notolychnus</i> Fraser-Brunner, 1949	94
I.1.18	<i>Notoscopelus</i> Günther, 1864	94
I.1.19	<i>Symbolophorus</i> Bolin & Wisner, 1959	96
I.1.20	<i>Taaningichthys</i> Bolin, 1959	97
I.2	Key to the Cape Verde genera of Sternoptychidae	98
II	Final art	107

List of Figures

1	Pen tool methodology. A: Reference image, B: Outline body shape, C: Complete head shape, D: Add body structures, E: Add depth and details, F: Final vector model.	13
2	Application of the Pattern Brush option in a soft finray.	14
3	A: Application of blend tool to finrays structure, using the Specified Steps option to determine the number of repetitions. B: Photophores following a path using the Replace Spine option.	15
4	Adobe Illustrator file size with and without symbols. Symbols were created for each fish in the figure.	16
5	Print screen of symbol inventory in Adobe Illustrator.	18
6	Symbols that were applied to Myctophidae. 1: Eyes symbol, 2: Pectoral fin, 3: Dorsal fin, 4: Caudal fin, 5: Pectoral fin, 6: Anal fin.	18
7	Genus <i>Benthosema</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Benthosema glaciale</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Benthosema glaciale</i> with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures. B1: Outline model for <i>Benthosema suborbitale</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Benthosema suborbitale</i> with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures, B4: Ventral view of diagnostic structures.	19
8	Genus <i>Bolinichthys</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Bolinichthys indicus</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Bolinichthys indicus</i> with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for <i>Bolinichthys photothorax</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Bolinichthys photothorax</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	20
9	Genus <i>Ceratoscopelus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Ceratoscopelus warmingii</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Ceratoscopelus warmingii</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	21
10	Genus <i>Diaphus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Diaphus holti</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Diaphus holti</i> with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for <i>Diaphus lucidus</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Diaphus lucidus</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	22
11	Genus <i>Diaphus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Diaphus molis</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Diaphus molis</i> with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for <i>Diaphus rafinesquei</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Diaphus rafinesquei</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	22
12	Genus <i>Diogenichthys</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Diogenichthys atlanticus</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Diogenichthys atlanticus</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	23
13	Genus <i>Hygophum</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Hygophum reinhardtii</i> with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures. B1: Outline model for <i>Hygophum taaningi</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Hygophum taaningi</i> with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures, B4: Ventral view of diagnostic structures.	24

14	Genus <i>Lampadena</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Lampadena pontifex</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Lampadena pontifex</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	25
15	Genus <i>Lampanyctus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Lampanictus alatus</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Lampanictus alatus</i> with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for <i>Lampanictus crocodilus</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Lampanictus crocodilus</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	26
16	Genus <i>Lampanyctus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Lampanictus intricarius</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Lampanictus intricarius</i> with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for <i>Lampanictus nobilis</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Lampanictus nobilis</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	26
17	Genus <i>Lepidophanes</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Lepidophanes guentheri</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Lepidophanes guentheri</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	27
18	Genus <i>Lobianchia</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Lobianchia dofleini</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Lobianchia dofleini</i> with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures, A4: Ventral view of diagnostic structures.	28
19	Genus <i>Nannobrachium</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Nannobrachium atrium</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Nannobrachium atrium</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	29
20	Symbols that were applied to Sternoptychidae. 1: Eye tubular, directed dorsally, 2: Dorsal spines, 3: Caudal fin, 4: Anal fin, 5: Large photophore fin, 6: Iliac spine, 7: Small photophore with black bord, 8: Small photophore without bord, 9: Lateral eyes, 10: Dorsal fin, 11: Valen photophores, 12: Pelvic fin, 13: Special photophore, 14: Pectoral fin.	31
21	Genus <i>Argyropelecus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Argyropelecus affins</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Argyropelecus affins</i> with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Dorsal shape smooth) B1: Outline model for <i>Argyropelecus gigas</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Argyropelecus gigas</i> with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Diagnostic structures (Dorsal shape irregular).	32
22	Genus <i>Argyropelecus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Argyropelecus olfersi</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Argyropelecus olfersi</i> with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Same sizes) B1: Outline model for <i>Argyropelecus acuelatus</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Argyropelecus acuelatus</i> with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Different sizes).	33
23	Genus <i>Argyropelecus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Argyropelecus hemigymnus</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Argyropelecus hemigymnus</i> with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Serrilhate). B1: Outline model for <i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i> with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Blunt).	34
24	Genus <i>Polyipnus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Polyipnus polli</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Polyipnus polli</i> with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Small dorsal spines).	35

25	Genus <i>Sternoptyx</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i> with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for <i>Sternoptyx pseudoobscura</i> , B2: Vector illustration <i>Sternoptyx pseudoobscura</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	36
26	Genus <i>Maurolicus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Maurolicus muelleri</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Maurolicus muelleri</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	37
27	Genus <i>Valenciennellus</i> . A1: Outline model for <i>Valenciennellus tripunctulatus</i> , A2: Vector illustration <i>Valenciennellus tripunctulatus</i> with symbols applied and corrected.	38
28	Example of final art in Adobe Photoshop for the family Myctophidae. A: <i>Benthosema glaciale</i> , B: <i>Benthosema suborbitale</i> , C: <i>Lampanictus intricarius</i> , D: <i>Diaphus lucidus</i> , E: <i>Nannobranchium atrium</i> , F: <i>Symbolophorus sp.</i> , G: <i>Myctophum sp.</i> H: <i>Lobianchia dofleini</i> , I: <i>Diogenichthys atlanticus</i> , J: <i>Lampanictus nobilis</i> , L: <i>Lepidophanes guentheri</i> , M: <i>Lampanictus alatus</i> , N: <i>Hygophum taaningi</i> , O: <i>Bolinichthys photothorax</i> , P: <i>Hygophum reinhardti</i> , Q: <i>Lampanictus crocodilus</i>	107
29	Example of final art in Adobe Photoshop for the family Sternoptychidae. A: <i>Argyropelecus aculeatus</i> , B: <i>Argyropelecus sladeni</i> , C: <i>Argyropelecus affinis</i> , D: <i>Argyropelecus gigas</i> , E: <i>Argyropelecus hemigymnus</i> , F: <i>Argyropelecus olfersi</i> , G: <i>Sternoptyx diaphana</i> , H: <i>Sternoptyx pseudoobscura</i> , I: <i>Polyipnus polli</i> , J: <i>Valenciennellus tripunctulatus</i> , L: <i>Maurolicus muelleri</i>	108

List of Tables

1	Number of species valid and illustrated from the families Myctophidae and Sternoptychidae (Froese & Pauly 2016).	17
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1 Introduction

1.1 Scientific illustration

Scientific illustration is a graphic domain influencing a vast, diversified and motivator field, joining science and art in one unique communication model without multiple meanings. It is an very useful and powerful tool for the learning process, education and personal knowledge, contributing to the progress of society/culture (as memory and repository of the visual understanding in different ages) (Correia 2011; Correia & Fernandes 2012; Pereira 2015).

As art reflects culture, scientific illustration reflects the findings of science and technology, as it takes the viewer to the often unobservable. Illustrations may help readers build useful mental models (Bayman & Mayer 1988; Mayer 1987), from molecules and viruses to the universe, from depiction of the internal anatomy of arthropods and plants to geologic cross sections and reconstruction of extinct life forms, ranging from realistic to abstract portrayal (Ford 1993). Shapes, anatomy, details, and concepts that cannot be conveyed with words form the essence of this art, however, in the same time, the image followed by the words, can make a text complete (Araújo *et al.* 2008).

Since the ancient times, humanity uses illustrations to communicate, as showed the many rupestrian drawings, to transmit the knowlegde to other people from the group and even other generations. One example is the rupestrian drawings in the Chauvet cave, located in Ardèche, France, which are dated from the Paliolithic superior, where it is possible to contemplate many drawings of several species, with reasonably good accuracy considering the age they were made (Combiér & Jouve 2014). During the XV century Portugal due the maritime exploration campaign, had high influence in the scientific illustration activities, which still constituted many of the basis of scientific illustration nowadays (Correia 2010) The curiosity collections from nobles from the XVI century generated the first illustrated catalogs in Europe, being considered ancestral compared with the illustrated books from today (Dance & Todd-White 1978).

During the XIX century, scientific illustration was extensively used during scientific expeditions, especially in botanic, since it was necessary to identify the potential use of plants for agriculture, pharmacy and chemistry (De Paula 1998a; Kury 1999). Throughout history, archaeologists, surgeons, engineers, and other researchers have sought to represent important scientific data in a manner that could be understood by others (specialists and not specialists). Illustrations have proven to be an effective means to achieve this goal, since they have the capability to display information more efficiently by omitting unimportant details. This sophistication is accomplished by directing attention to relevant features or details, simplifying complex features, or exposing features that were formerly obscured (Winkenbach & Salesin 1994).

With popularization of photography, it was questioned if scientific illustration still a usefull tool, which in actually it still is, since the skilled scientific illustrator can clarify multiple focal depths and overlapping layers, emphasize important details, and perfect specimens can be reconstructed from a series of preserved specimens where no single specimen is fully intact — results unattainable through photography. In fact, the photograph of one species or

specimen is rarely representative as a model for species. Yet there is still no mechanized alternative for an illustrator's unique talents and keen point of view. Though photography is an incredibly useful and impressive tool, it has its limitations. "That's where we illustrators get to fill in the blanks. Indeed, many natural science and medical publications use scientific illustrations in place of photographs because of the illustrations' educational and communicative ability (Hodges 1989). The scientific illustration act as a synthesis of graphic information that is accurate according to the communication and the target public that is destined (Correia & Fernandes 2012).

Understanding how illustrations work in science cannot be done in a generalized manner, it must be grounded in the dynamics of a specific discipline (Mishra & Mishra 2009), as it is produced for a specific kind of visual communication in the sciences. This communication can pass from scientist to colleague, teacher to student, or research foundation to layman. Thus, scientific illustration is a communication tool that allows the transaction between different kind of knowledges and speed up the flux of information in a fluid way, without disruptions (Correia 2011)

The graphic register (Codify in illustration the reality or symbol, which uses of pure abstraction, as the writing) consist in a cognitive process and facilitates the understanding/perception of the reality and the sociocultural/scientific knowledge since the beginning of human history. This codification follow and evolve with the understanding of the perception of the reality, being it organic, empiric or scientific (Correia & Fernandes 2012). The illustration it is not just the code - in points, lines and color - that gives value to the knowledge (Rodrigues 2010), but also becomes memory. Previous studies suggests that "Scholars are trained to analyze words. But primates are visual animals, and the key concepts and their history often lies in iconography" (Gould 1992). Thus, humans as a visual entity, it is by the vision it can interact faster with the reality that it surrounds and stimulate, due the same cognitive mechanisms related and improved by evolution.

In practical terms, scientific illustration is important to catalog and represent biological diversity; for example, insects that carry prejudice (Stubbs, Falk, *et al.* 1983), aquatic animals of economic importance (Faust & Gullledge 2002), plant seeds that are considered weeds (Jepson 1993), or plants or fungi of agricultural and medical importance (Larone 2011). Medical illustrations elucidate how new surgeries are performed or the anatomy of domestic animals as well as humans (Sobotta 1957).

Traditionally the most common medias of representation included black and white (pen and ink, scratchboard, Coquille board), continuous tone (ink wash, carbon dust, graphite pencil), and color illustration techniques (watercolor, gouache, and acrylics; colored pencil; mixed media). With the advent of new technologies as the "digital revolution," the use of computers and software applications to produce digital illustrations has been added to the artist's toolbox, playing an important role in allowing the creation of science representation by more communication practitioners, scientists, and the public.

Digital illustration brings functional advantages, since the drawing it is done in digital environment. Two types of software applications can be used to produce digital illustrations, vector or object- oriented applications and bitmap or raster applications. In vector applications, mathematical expressions or vectors define "objects," such as lines, curves, and

shapes. Vector applications produce drawings or illustrations with crisp edges, uniformly smooth lines, smooth changes in tone or color and no resolution limitations (Kaufman 1993). Vector applications are represented by drawing programs such as Adobe Illustrator. Vector drawings can also be “rasterized” and then edited in image-editing applications; but in bitmap format. In bitmap applications, a virtual grid of pixels is used to represent an image. Pixels are the smallest individual components of a digital image. On a computer monitor, each pixel appears as a small square with a fixed size, location, and color or grayscale value; and it can be edited individually. Bitmapped images are resolution dependent: the resolution of the image produced is dependent on the display device (computer monitor, printer) and the inherent resolution of the bitmap image. Applications as Adobe Photoshop, are ideal for editing in bitmap format.

1.2 Taxonomy and biological diversity

Taxonomy is the field of research devoted to naming and describing living organisms, providing basic vocabulary and understanding about the many components of biodiversity (Wheeler 2007; Zhang 2008). Historically, the Swedish botanist Carl Linnaeus (1707–1778) ushered in a new era of taxonomy. With his major works *Systema Naturae* (von Linné 1766), he revolutionized modern taxonomy, implementing a standardized binomial naming system for animals and plants, which proved to be an elegant solution to a chaotic and disorganized taxonomic literature. Despite essential to our understanding of the natural history, taxonomy is much underappreciated aspect of scientific research.

The scientific illustration acquired a new role of intervention, assuming itself as another kind of scientific language, with more iconical and intuitive grammatical but equally capable (in organization, structure and synthesis of the message to be transmitted), which allows to catalog and related the reality of the live organisms and natural environment, being more persuasive by the visual rhetoric phenomenon. Since the XVI century, the plants are anymore represented as a whole natural organism, but represented part by part avoiding overlays, and your most important structures highlighted (the flower, the fruit, the leafs, the roots) for a better understanding (Ogilvie 2003). For the animals, the same strategy is applied (illustration of wings, body sections, etc).

The task of routine species identification has four significant limitations. First, both phenotypic plasticity and genetic variability in the characters employed for species recognition can lead to incorrect identifications. Second, this approach overlooks morphologically cryptic taxa, which are common in many groups (Jarman *et al.* 2000; Knowlton 1993). Third, since morphological keys are often effective only for a particular life stage or gender, many individuals cannot be identified. Finally, although modern interactive versions represent a major advance, the use of keys often demands such a high level of expertise that misdiagnoses are common.

In the case of deep-sea taxonomists often find themselves faced by some extra problems, representative samples might be hard to obtain: Not only does sampling require more logistic and financial support than in most other habitats, but also the mere size of the deep sea rather impedes adequate sampling. Besides, abundances are low in the deep sea and

species are often rare or patchily distributed. This means that while nearly every sample may contain species new to science, these are often represented by just one or few individuals, generally not considered to be ideal for a comprehensive description. However, resampling an area to increase the number of available specimens is often prevented by logistic constraints (Broekeland & George 2009).

Some deep-sea areas, particularly in the Southern Hemisphere and throughout the Indian Ocean and in Indonesia, should reveal many new taxa from increased collecting efforts. Molecular genetic studies are proving valuable in phylogenetic and phylogeographic analyses as well as in species' population analyses, but these relatively new techniques are not uncovering large numbers of new or cryptic taxa.

The most basic requirement for people studying and working on aspects of biodiversity is the availability of species identification guides. They are not only important as a resource, but also because they enable many more scientists to begin to recognise and study previously little known species. Without such guides it is impractical for most people to know or study a group of species and consequently the biology, ecology and potential economic value of these species will remain unknown. People need rapid access to species identification guides, and funding agencies and publishers must know which guides are most urgently needed to fill taxonomic and geographic gaps.

Considering that fisheries have never been so heavily harvested and that aquaculture is rapidly growing, one may expect concomitant growth in understanding what biodiversity exists in the oceans. However, there is no evidence of increased resources to identify and inventory marine biodiversity. Indeed, members of the scientific community have asserted that expertise in the form of taxonomists able to identify, describe and classify species is declining (Boero 2001; Giangrande 2003). However, these assertions are anecdotal and unsubstantiated. Where data have been provided, such as for Chile (Simonetti 1997), South Africa (Sluys, Gibbons, *et al.* 1999), the USA (Winston 1988) and globally (Rodríguez 2000), they show that more taxonomists are needed to address the mismatch between the number of species in certain taxa and the corresponding number of taxonomists, but do not demonstrate a decline in the number of taxonomists. On the contrary, in Latin America, notably in Brazil, there has been increased employment and training in taxonomy since the 1980s (de Carvalho *et al.* 2005).

A review (Costello *et al.* 2006) showed that the identification guides geographical coverage was very uneven, with 52% of the titles particular to northern Europe (the British Isles, North Sea and Scandinavia), 22% to the Mediterranean and 11% to the Atlantic–Lusitanian region (Bay of Biscay to Morocco and the Atlantic archipelagos). No series considered the deep-sea fauna in particular, being the guides to deep-sea fauna limited to selected groups of Mollusca, Tunicata, Crustacea and Echinodermata.

There are both taxonomic and geographic gaps in the availability of up-to-date marine species identification guides. The large, common, and/or ecologically significant species are covered in several to many guides. In contrast, many of the smaller, rarer or taxonomically difficult to identify species as some groups of mesopelagic fishes are not covered in any of the guides listed. Yet, these species may be of great importance to biodiversity, ecosystem function and marine resources. Although many identification guides are available for the

north of Europe (the North and Baltic Seas) in which the marine fauna and flora is least diverse, there are considerably fewer guides for those regions of Europe in which the marine fauna and flora is most diverse (the Mediterranean, the Atlantic archipelagos, the deep sea). Thus, the taxonomic and geographic gaps that most urgently require attention are the smaller sized taxa in the southern European seas (both Atlantic and Mediterranean).

The advantage of electronic publication is that species identification is possible through electronic keys that can be more user-friendly and functional than traditional paper keys. Thus, 'biodiversity informatics', the use of information technology in biodiversity data management, must join molecular techniques (e.g. DNA bar-coding) as a new tool in taxonomy. Informatics and molecular tools are not alternatives to taxonomy. The need to identify species in practical ways still requires taxonomic descriptions and images, type specimens as standards for comparative analysis, and a species naming system that enables communication of 'what it is'. Biodiversity informatics can increase the visibility and availability of taxonomic knowledge and its associated data, thereby facilitating more cost-effective use of resources.

"Keys are compiled by those who do not need them for those who cannot use them" (Lobanov 2003).

1.3 The deep sea

In the early 19th century, when the waters of oceans were first sampled at depth, scientists generally believed that the deep ocean was depleted of life. However, soon these theories have been proved wrong; from pioneering work in the 19th century, until deep ocean exploration in modern times, a vast diversity and abundance of marine organisms have been described (Gage & Tyler 1991).

The deep sea is the lowest layer in the ocean, existing below the thermocline and above the seabed, at a depth of 1000 fathoms (1800 m) or more. Little or no light penetrates this part of the ocean, being insufficient to penetrate to allow vision in even the most sensitive fish (Denton 1990), and most of the organisms that live there rely for subsistence on falling organic matter produced in the photic zone. The second source of light in the deep-sea is the bioluminescence produced by the animals themselves, whose peak emission is usually, but not always close to the same wavelengths as the remaining sunlight (Mensing & Case 1990). Although such bioluminescence is rare in terrestrial and fresh water organisms (Herring 1996), in the deep-sea it is the norm, with over 80% of deep-oceanic species having the ability to produce their own light. These emissions serve a variety of functions including intra and inter specific signalling, counterillumination camouflage, a means of startling predators, and attractant to prey, and a way of simply illuminating their darkened world (Herring 1996).

The immense variety of life forms in the deep sea has been a source of public and scientific fascination, due to the very different shapes of the organisms there found. The environmental characteristics, as high pressure and absence of sunlight, required these species to have adaptations, being most deep sea fishes with high bone and musculature reduction as it facilitates the neutral buoyancy (Moyle & Joseph 2004; Yancey 2011). Unlike the firm bodied fish that are commonly encountered in shallow water and are adapted to rapid movement,

many deep sea fishes are eel like, maintaining a minimal profile while moving sinuously through the water seeking prey. Others, such as the anglerfish, are somewhat blob-like and drift with ambient currents. In steady of actively looking for a prey, many predators use lures to attract their prey and have extensible jaws and large stomachs so they may consume weak prey almost large as themselves. Their metabolic rates are also very low compared to surface fishes, possibly due the lack of light (Childress *et al.* 1980), thus, where there is visually no ambient light, reaction distances are much reduced, and there is no advantage to maintaining strong burst swimming capacity. The smaller midwater fishes have adopted a highly energy efficiency ecological strategy, by drastically reducing their locomotory capacity and associated metabolic costs, they can maintain high growth rates in a resource poor environment.

1.4 Seamounts

Seamounts are unique environments and hotspots of biodiversity and endemism in the deep sea often showing higher diversity and biomass, compared to the surrounding abyssal plain. As underwater mountains, they rise at least 1000 m from the abyssal floor of the ocean in about 4000 m depth but do not reach the surface (Kitchingman *et al.* 2007). Only few seamounts have been sampled so far (Stocks 2004), to date around 300 seamounts (Seamounts Online, <http://seamounts.sdsc.edu>), being the current 535 species of seamount fishes representing only about 2% of the over 28400 recent fish species on earth. A distinct guild of fish species that aggregate around seamounts and that differ markedly from other deepwater species in their relatively high levels of food consumption and body plan suite for strong swimming performance. Although located in the deep sea, they are inhabited by a demersal ichthyofauna commonly associated with shelf and slope areas (Kukuev 2004). However, these demersal fish species have been generally found to be rare in larval fish assemblages over seamounts (Boehlert & Mundy 1993). Seamounts are of interest for ichthyogeography as their demersal fish fauna can be interpreted with respect to faunistic linkages and dispersal ("stepping stones") (Monteiro *et al.* 2008), improving our understanding the zoogeographic patterns. However, their biology is poorly known, often only assumed from the morphology of the type specimens (Froese & Sampang 2004). Seamounts are also of potential interest for fisheries (Kukuev 2004), or have already been exploited with temporary commercial success regardless of the vulnerability of deep-sea ecosystems (Clark & Koslow 2007), being 151 seamount fishes are known to be exploited commercially, despite this lack of information needed for sustainable use. This habitat extremely low productivity combined with a habit of fishes in this areas maintaining themselves in highly localized aggregations has made this areas exceptionally susceptible to overfishing. This situation is aggravated by the fact that many seamounts are in international waters, where there is no management (Froese & Sampang 2004). In this context, we studied 2 relevant families present in Senghor seamount, Myctophidae and Sternoptichidae.

1.5 Family Myctophidae

The Family Myctophidae, also commonly designated by lanternfishes, is a family that belongs to the Order Myctophiformes. It is highly diversified, being counted until the moment 252 species, distributed for over 30 genera (32 to 36, the literature diverges) (Catul *et al.* 2011; Davis *et al.* 2014; Moser *et al.* 1984). Its name comes from the Greek word “mykter” (nose) and “ophis” (serpent), and many species indeed possess a developed snout. Myctophids count up as the vertebrates that contribute the most to the oceans’ biomass (Ahlstrom *et al.* 1976), and as 75% of all the mesopelagic fishes captured by trawl, notwithstanding their reduced size (commonly smaller than 15 cm), weight (2 to 6 g) and longevity (1 to 5 years). It is an ubiquitous family in all oceans (except the Arctic); its diversity may be an biogeographic indicator of an specific area. They are equally found in any areas of high productivity, frequently dominating all the phases of the life cycle of the ichthyofauna total, from larvae, to juveniles, to adults (Hanel *et al.* 2010).

Myctophids possess adaptations to the pelagic layer in which they’re found, such as swimbladders, which allow them to perform the diel vertical migrations (DVM), moving from depths between 250 m and 1000 m during the day until 100 m – 20 m during the night. They can even tolerate the low oxygen levels of the mesopelagic layer, and have the necessary visual adaptations to the reduced irradiation rates of the inferior pelagic layers, particularly to distinguish the bioluminescent signals of their congeners (Turner *et al.* 2009). Due the DVM, they can a significant role as consumers of zooplankton in the food web (Lancraft *et al.* 1989). They occupy the third level and are consumers of the second order. They are an important food source for the predators of higher trophic levels like benthopelagic fish (Bulman *et al.* 2002), seabirds (Guinet *et al.* 1996), for seals (Cherel *et al.* 1997) and squid (Phillips *et al.* 2001). Thus, in any estimation of energy transport within the pelagic system, it is important to include analyses of the individual diet composition of the mesopelagic fish and their rates of food consumption. Though rich in proteins, minerals and oils, difficulties in their processing (precisely due to their body oils) make them, as for now, unlikely for human use (Vipin *et al.* 2011), but still can be used in animal food and fertilizers.

The photophores, even though non-exclusive to this family, are from their most distinctive characteristics (hence the designation “lanternfishes”) – so far, only the species *Taaningichthys paurolychnus* is indicated as not possessing photophores (Catul *et al.* 2011); not depending from symbiosis with other species they’re complex structures, constituted by modified scales, which contain photogenic tissue. They are distributed vertically, emitting blue-green-yellow light, and are specific to each species, sometimes indicating even sexual dimorphism (Catul *et al.* 2011; Haddock *et al.* 2010). Their location and number work in this way as a faithful instrument to identify the fishes’ species. Some species possess also spots of luminous tissue, being the genus *Diaphus sp.* one of the most remarkable in this characteristic.

1.6 Family Sternoptychidae

The Order Stomiiformes includes the Family Sternoptychidae. The fishes of this family, commonly designated as “hatchet-fishes”, are organisms with size generally inferior to 10

cm, with deeply compressed bodies, being present a profound slope in the abdominal area, that originated the designation “hatchet-fishes”. Hatchet-fishes are distributed in 70 species and 10 genera, being in several bathypelagic areas of the globe their numbers exceeded only by elements of the Family Gonostomatidae. This family has ultimately a great variability in intergenera corporal morphology (Lima *et al.* 2011), being the “keel” more or less accentuated, according to the species. Hatchet-fishes have big-sized, sometimes grouped, ventral photophores, which are important in their identification (Ahlstrom 1974), as in Family Myctophidae; in some cases, they may be the most useful tool to distinguish the specimens of this family from the specimens of other Stomiiformes, particularly from gonostomatids, even considering osteological comparisons. In the same way, they can be identified through their gillrakers’ number (Weitzman 1974). Particularly, on the top of their dorso it’s a “blade” constituted by united pterygiophores (the internal bony supporters of the finrays). The snout is short; they’re also holders of orientally directed eyes and mouths, being the first tubular, an adaptation to the low luminosity levels (Harold, 2002). These are indicators that the hatchet-fishes perform DVM diel vertical migrations, as many others mesopelagic fishes. Most of these fishes are mesopelagic when adult, though some species are bathy- or bentopelagic. This distribution, as the bodily characteristics mentioned above, indicate that hatchet-fishes may predate their food (copepods, amongst other constituents of the zooplankton) from below (Lima *et al.* 2011), and the records do indicate that the members of this family locate themselves commonly at depths superior to the members of the Family Myctophidae (Badcock & Merrett 1976).

1.7 Why apply scientific illustration?

The study of deep-sea fish fauna is hampered by a lack of data due to the difficulty and high cost incurred in its surveys and collections. Additionally, most of the collected deep-sea animals succumb as the result of decompression and exposure to the high-temperature surface seawater (Koyama & Aizawa 2000). Thus, the animals must be preserved for further studies, being the most common solution used is formalin, since is inexpensive, it is generally available and specimens almost never decay in it, however, it has a tendency to make specimens become brittle if the solution is too strong, and tends to fade out certain colors rapidly (Etheridge 1958). Due this difficulties discussed previously, studying fishes sampled from deep sea could be very challenging, This work aims to produce a vector illustrated identification key of these families. Vector images gives a formulaic approach to drawing, where each image can be sized and scaled repeatedly and limitlessly without losing resolution. Additionally, the ability to select individual components of a path gives vector a high flexibility to edition, where key features from a species can be changed, representing several species, with basis on a model illustration from a family, thus, the guide is always ready to be updated. We aim to provide a tool for species identification, but also to show the importance of scientific illustration for biodiversity studies and scientific communication.

Taxonomy supports itself in the systematization of blocks contain information of diagnostic value, centered in specific structures or body sections (different in terms of morphology and mophometry). This methodology was adopted in the concept of organize and sym-

bol inventory which can be adapted to each pattern, being each element morphoadaptative (Cerviño, et. al 2015) and the group of this elements add to the body shape, consisting in an archeotype (Correia 2011) or representative icon of the species.

2 Material and methods

2.1 Sampling and identification of species

The samples were obtained from Senghor Seamount (Cape Verde Archipelago), in two cruises on R. V. Poseidon – P423 and P446 (in December of 2011 and February of 2013, respectively), using a IKMT net (Isaacs-Kidd mid-water trawl) having the external net 75 mm, the inner net 16 mm, and the codend 1mm, the latter being covered by plastic multifilaments with 19 mm mesh (Christiansen 2011, 2013). The sampled individuals were kept in formaldehyde. In the lab, samples were transferred to ethanol 70% and identified using available literature (Reiner 1996; Whitehead PJP 1984–1986).

Resorting to various works (Backus *et al.* 1977; dos Santos 2003; Hartel & Craddock 2002; Hulley & DuHamel 2009; Kawaguchi & Aior 1977; Lima *et al.* 2011; Reiner 1996; Tatsuta *et al.* 2014; Zahuranec 2000), and also personal observations, standardized and detailed morphological descriptions of the taxa were made, accentuating the implicit characteristics of the families and the genera, and thus reducing greatly the size of the species' descriptions. The output of this work, an updated taxonomic key for both Families to the Central Eastern Atlantic, emphasizing the species registered to the Cape Verde area, was compiled from the work of several authors (dos Santos 2003; Hanel *et al.* 2010; Kawaguchi & Aior 2003; Lima *et al.* 2011; Olivar P *et al.* 1999; Tatsuta *et al.* 2014; Vakily *et al.* 2002; Zahuranec 2000). The author of this study did not carry out this part of the study sampling and identification of species, but just the managed the systematization with the aim to implement a new tool with taxonomical approach to facilitate the correct identification of the species.

2.2 Collecting information

Before start any scientific illustration, it is necessary to collect the maximum of information possible (Pereira 2015). The starting point and the main reference will be the sample we have present in the lab. It was carefully observed to identify possible damages, miss formations, colour decaying. Additionally, identify sexual dimorfism and ontogenetic variations of the animal, due to changes in morphological patterns. All pictures were taken with the camera, with a ruler under the fish, to be possible to keep a scale for the drawing.

Suplementar material was also important, being external sources as the Fishbase, pictures from other papers or even sent by another specialists raised the accuracy of the final work. As normally happens to animals from deep sea, when bring to surface, changes can happend in your morphology and very often parts can be damage, specially the most fragil ones as the fin rays. Thus, it is necessary to combine the information from the pictures of the specimens caught by the campaing with other references, being other pictures or schematic drawings, from trustful sources. The illustrations were done by the same person (Felipe Ribas), to keep the same visual standard and to maintains visual approach consistence e uniformity.

2.3 Adobe Illustrator

Adobe Illustrator is a vector graphics editor developed and marketed by Adobe Systems. Unlike the familiar gif, jpeg, tiff, saving formats – known as raster images – vector images are not made up of a grid of pixels, being instead, created by paths, a combination of a starting point and an ending point with a combination of shapes, angles and lines in-between (Kaufman 1993). These paths relate to each other by mathematical formulas, allowing them to be scaled and rescaled infinitely.

2.3.1 Artboard size

For all illustrations, the artboard size was A4. As it is a vector, it can be later edit to become any size necessary to the target publication. It was also faster and easier in terms of computer process to work in smaller virtual environment, as it require less memory RAM from the computer.

2.3.2 Pen tool

The drawing begins by using one of the Illustrator's most powerful features, the Pen tool. To digitally "ink" the template layer, the Pen tool creates paths to which strokes of different line weights and color (usually black) are applied. It is wise to turn off the fill option while vectorizing, as it can overlap slices of the image. Keep track of all the items in your document window, as items get hidden under larger items, and selecting artwork becomes difficult. Layers provide a way to organize all the items, being an easy way to select, hide, lock, and change the appearance attributes of artwork. It is also possible to create template layers, which can be used to trace artwork, and exchange layers with Adobe Photoshop. The final illustration takes on the look of a traditional pen-and-ink illustration. The ability to select individual components of a path (by direct selection of anchor points and adjusting direction lines) allows for precise changes in the shape of paths. Targeting paths to different layers adds editing flexibility to the illustration. By varying the stroke weight or by using the *Outline Stroke* feature, weighted lines can be produced so that the illustration takes on shape and depth. In addition to the Pen tool, Illustrator's Pencil, Line, and Brush tools also create paths. By varying the length and stroke of paths, these tools can be used to create digital stipples or crosshatches. Custom brushes can also be created, for example to produce setae or scales, even with setal sockets, that are drawn as single paths.

An easier way to start it is organizing the work by layers. First, open in one layer the specimen photograph you plan to trace in Adobe Illustrator, this will serve as your reference to scale. The pictures of the specimen caught were always the basis of the vectorization. Photographs can be a valuable aid in drawing, but when used as the only reference by an illustrator not familiar with the subject, the result may be flat or distorted (Wood & McDonnell 1994), reason why it is recommended some time investment from the illustrator to be used to the different arquetypes (models or icon types) of the species that will be illustrated (Pereira 2015).

Other references can complement the missing or damaged structures from the fish. Fishes were illustrated from lateral view, following the scientific ichthyological standards (Ridgway 1938). With a double click on the layer with the photo in the Layer Panel, and name the layer (Reference Image). Before closing the dialog box, also click the 'Dim Images to' box and put a number in between 80%-70%. Also, make sure you click the 'Lock' layer box, so the layer will not be affected by actions happening in other layers. It was created a second layer where the paths will be drawn by the Pen Tool. Drawing each structure separately (segments, membranes, spines, eyes) maximizes the possibilities of further editions and also make the work more fluid. When necessary, specific structures as the photophores, were pointed from different views (as dorsal, ventral angle or frontal). In this layer it was included the basis of the fish shape, eye, lateral line, pectoral finrays and head parts. Due the difficult to find good references, the fish scales were not illustrated. When there are structures with a repetitive pattern, as the finrays segmentations, create just a template of the form, this will be edited later by the Pattern Brush.

Figure 1: Pen tool methodology. A: Reference image, B: Outline body shape, C: Complete head shape, D: Add body structures, E: Add depth and details, F: Final vector model.

2.3.3 Pattern brush

Pattern brush is used to create a frame for the artwork that is fully adjustable, without skewing the shape or contours of the frame. Pattern brushes paint a pattern made up of separate sections, or tiles. When using a Pattern brush to artwork, different tiles of the pattern are applied to different sections of the path, depending on where the section falls on the path (the end, middle, or corner). Pattern brushes can be useful to create segmentation patterns, for example, the segments of fish finrays.

The process can be divided in 3 parts.

1. Draw the Side Tile: This establishes the basic pattern to be repeated on the sides of the shape, being the most important. As the elements being drawn to the tile, it also creates guides on either side of the tile. After the wished pattern is done, it is grouped together and repeat it [use the command (Alt+D) to repeat patterns more easily] on either side just to make sure the tiles are completely seamless. Transfer the pattern created to the brush pattern box.
2. Draw the End Tiles: As it happens, the two extra side tiles on either side are perfectly placed to create the beginning and end tiles.
3. Draw the Corner Tile(s): The corner tiles are the trickiest to create, but they provide the anchor of the pattern and often carry the style of the entire pattern. As such, it is important to get them right. There are two corner tiles, an outer corner and an inner corner.

It is also possible to use vary width profile to adjust the shape of the pattern. To keep the pattern shape when you adjust the size, expand the object (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Application of the Pattern Brush option in a soft finray.

2.3.4 Graphic style

A graphic style is a set of reusable appearance attributes. Graphic styles allow you to quickly change the look of an object; for example, changing the fill and stroke color, alter the transparency, and apply effects in just one step. All the changes applied with graphic styles are completely reversible.

Graphic styles can be used in objects, groups, and layers. When the graphic style is applied to a group or layer, every object in the group or layer takes on the attributes of the graphic style. Assuming a graphic style that consists of 50% opacity, when applied this option to a layer, all objects in or added to that layer will appear 50% opaque. However, if the object is moved out of the layer, the object's appearance reverts to its previous opacity.

2.3.5 Blend tool

Blend Tool is a Live tool, meaning that it can change its object or shape, its color or position, and the blend will be updated live. It is possible to create blends either with the *Blend Tool* or the *Make Blend command*. Even though Adobe has blurred many of the lines between Photoshop and Illustrator over the years, they have kept some of them very distinct, being the *Blend tool* is one of those distinct differences (Kloskowski 2004).

This tool fills in the space between two objects with intermediate steps, to create a smooth transition. In this case, the intermediate objects are changing size to blend from one point of known elevation to another. Blends can also be done along a curved path to help better represent the shape of the underlying object using the option *Replace Spine*.

Blend tool can be applied to biological models, keeping the same style pattern between illustrations, being necessary just few comands to change the characteristics of one specie to another from the same genus. In this study we used this function to create proportional distances and an smooth change of size in finrays. The number of structures are chosen in the *Blend tool options* (Figure 3). The blend tool can also be used in future implementation of taxonomical database, keeping the specimen shape constant and just changing the structures with few commands to adequate to the species description.

As the Blend Tool takes a lot of memory RAM, which it may slow down the computer, an wise way to work it is avoid to use it in files full of objects, being an easy option to create symbols from the different blend.

Figure 3: A: Application of blend tool to finrays structure, using the Specified Steps option to determine the number of repetitions. B: Photophores following a path using the Replace Spine option.

2.3.6 Symbols

A symbol is an art object that you can reuse in a document. For example, if you create a symbol from an eye, you can then add instances of that symbol multiple times to your artwork without actually adding the complex art multiple times. Each symbol instance is linked to the symbol in the Symbols panel or to a symbols library. Using symbols can save you time and greatly reduce file size, which can significantly slow down your workflow, as it can be saved in the symbols area editing, zooming of the screen and just saving the large files may take several minutes, being also often the reason of application crashes resulting in the loss of all or part of the work (Figure 4).

Nearly any object can be made into a symbol. A couple of exceptions are art that is not

linked and groups of graphics. To open the Symbols panel, click on the button that looks like a clover, located in the menu on the right side of the Illustrator screen. The Symbol Libraries provide a clean way to organize the symbols that you acquire. To open them, click on the Symbols Library menu in the far left of your Symbols tools, or go to Window : Symbol Libraries : [symbol]. The library that you select will open in a new window. When you choose a symbol from an open library, it is automatically added to the Symbols panel. Symbols panel menu and select “Save Symbol Library.” Name your symbol library, and save it to the default Symbols folder. You can now find your new library folder in Symbols Library Menu : User Defined : [symbol].

In case it necessary to edit the symbol, the “Break Link to Symbol” button simply turns the symbol that you’ve placed on your artboard back into a regular graphic. While changes such as move, scale, rotate, reflect and skew (shear) can be made to a symbol’s instance on the artboard without changing the original symbol in the panel, more advanced edits will affect both the instance and the symbol if they are linked. By clicking on the “Break Link to Symbol” button, you can now modify the symbol in the panel without affecting the graphic on your artboard. The opposite is also true: edits made to an instance with a broken link will no longer affect the symbol.

File size

Without symbols : 19,4 MB

With symbols : 9,37 MB

Figure 4: Adobe Illustrator file size with and without symbols. Symbols were created for each fish in the figure.

3 Results

In total, 30 species were illustrated, 19 from the family Myctophidae and 11 from the family Sternoptychidae (Table 1). The identification key was based on the book (Whitehead PJP 1984–1986) and modify for the drawings composition, which are displayed in appendix section.

Table 1: Number of species valid and illustrated from the families Myctophidae and Sternoptychidae (Froese & Pauly 2016).

Family	Genus	Species valid	Species illustrated
Myctophidae	Benthoosema	5	2
Myctophidae	Bolinichthys	7	2
Myctophidae	Ceratoscopelus	3	1
Myctophidae	Diaphus	77	4
Myctophidae	Diogenichthys	3	1
Myctophidae	Hygophum	9	2
Myctophidae	Lampadena	9	1
Myctophidae	Lampanyctus	22	3
Myctophidae	Lepidophanes	2	1
Myctophidae	Lobianchia	2	1
Myctophidae	Nannobranchium	17	1
Sternoptychidae	Argyropelecus	7	6
Sternoptychidae	Polyipnus	33	1
Sternoptychidae	Sternoptyx	4	2
Sternoptychidae	Maurolicus	15	1
Sternoptychidae	Valenciennellus	2	1

3.1 Vector symbols

In total, 52 symbols were created, divided in 2 libraries, one for the family Myctophidae and other for the family Sternoptychidae (Figure 5). Each symbol already contain blend features when necessary, as the case of fin rays and lateral line, which can be accessed by the option break symbol.

Figure 5: Print screen of symbol inventory in Adobe Illustrator.

3.2 Family Myctophidae

All species of Myctophidae caught in the 2 campaigns were vectorized and symbols were applied. Overall 6 symbols were used for the outline models of the species Myctophidae (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Symbols that were applied to Myctophidae. 1: Eyes symbol, 2: Pectoral fin, 3: Dorsal fin, 4: Caudal fin, 5: Pectoral fin, 6: Anal fin.

3.2.1 Genus *Benthoosema*

There are currently 5 species valid for the *Benthoosema* genus, 2 species were vectorized (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Genus *Benthoosema*. A1: Outline model for *Benthoosema glaciale*, A2: Vector illustration *Benthoosema glaciale* with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures. B1: Outline model for *Benthoosema suborbitale*, B2: Vector illustration *Benthoosema suborbitale* with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures, B4: Ventral view of diagnostic structures.

3.2.2 Genus *Bolinichthys*

There are currently 7 species valid in this genus *Bolinichthys* which 2 species were vectorized (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Genus *Bolinichthys*. A1: Outline model for *Bolinichthys indicus*, A2: Vector illustration *Bolinichthys indicus* with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for *Bolinichthys photothorax*, B2: Vector illustration *Bolinichthys photothorax* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.2.3 Genus *Ceratoscopelus*

There are currently three species valid in this genus which, just 1 specie was vectorized (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Genus *Ceratoscopelus*. A1: Outline model for *Ceratoscopelus warmingii*, A2: Vector illustration *Ceratoscopelus warmingii* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.2.4 Genus *Diaphus*

Diaphus is a genus of lanternfishes, with 77 species valid. For the *Diaphus* genus, 4 species were vectorized (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Genus *Diaphus*. A1: Outline model for *Diaphus holti*, A2: Vector illustration *Diaphus holti* with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for *Diaphus lucidus*, B2: Vector illustration *Diaphus lucidus* with symbols applied and corrected.

Figure 11: Genus *Diaphus*. A1: Outline model for *Diaphus molis*, A2: Vector illustration *Diaphus molis* with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for *Diaphus rafinesquei*, B2: Vector illustration *Diaphus rafinesquei* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.2.5 Genus *Diogenichthys*

There are currently three species valid for the *Diogenichthys* genus, which 1 specie was vectorized (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Genus *Diogenichthys*. A1: Outline model for *Diogenichthys atlanticus*, A2: Vector illustration *Diogenichthys atlanticus* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.2.6 Genus *Hygophum*

There are currently nine valid species in this genus. For the *Hygophum* genus, 2 species were vectorized (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Genus *Hygophum*. A1: Outline model for *Hygophum reinhardtii*, A2: Vector illustration *Hygophum reinhardtii* with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures. B1: Outline model for *Hygophum taaningi*, B2: Vector illustration *Hygophum taaningi* with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures, B4: Ventral view of diagnostic structures.

3.2.7 Genus *Lampadena*

For the *Lampadena* genus, 1 species was vectorized (Figure 14).

Lampadena pontifex

A1

A2

Figure 14: Genus *Lampadena*. A1: Outline model for *Lampadena pontifex*, A2: Vector illustration *Lampadena pontifex* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.2.8 Genus *Lampanyctus*

There are currently 22 species valid in this genus. For the *Lampanyctus* genus, 4 species were vectorized (Figure 15).

Figure 15: Genus *Lampanyctus*. A1: Outline model for *Lampanyctus alatus*, A2: Vector illustration *Lampanyctus alatus* with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for *Lampanyctus crocodilus*, B2: Vector illustration *Lampanyctus crocodilus* with symbols applied and corrected.

Figure 16: Genus *Lampanyctus*. A1: Outline model for *Lampanyctus intricarius*, A2: Vector illustration *Lampanyctus intricarius* with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for *Lampanyctus nobilis*, B2: Vector illustration *Lampanyctus nobilis* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.2.9 Genus *Lepidophanes*

There are currently two species valid in this genus. For the *Lepidophanes* genus, 1 species was vectorized (Figure 17).

Lepidophanes guentheri

Figure 17: Genus *Lepidophanes*. A1: Outline model for *Lepidophanes guentheri*, A2: Vector illustration *Lepidophanes guentheri* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.2.10 Genus *Lobianchia*

There are currently two species valid in this genus. For the *Lobianchia* genus, 1 species was vectorized (Figure 18).

Lobianchia dofleini

Figure 18: Genus *Lobianchia*. A1: Outline model for *Lobianchia dofleini*, A2: Vector illustration *Lobianchia dofleini* with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Dorsal view of diagnostic structures, A4: Ventral view of diagnostic structures.

3.2.11 Genus *Nannobrachium*

There are currently 17 species valid in this genus. For the *Nannobrachium* genus, 1 specie was vectorized (Figure 19).

Nannobranchium atrum

Figure 19: Genus *Nannobranchium*. A1: Outline model for *Nannobranchium atrum*, A2: Vector illustration *Nannobranchium atrum* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.3 Family Sternoptychidae

Symbols were applied to vectorized fishes from Sternoptychidae family. This family has more variable body shapes compared to Myctophidae, being the body narrow, laterally compressed, deeply keeled and roughly disc-shaped bodies, somewhat resembling a hatchet (with the thorax being the "blade" and the caudal peduncle being the "handle"); the pelvis is rotated to a vertical position. The members of the disputed subfamily Maurolicinae (*Maurolicus* and *Valenciennellus*) and have a more conventional fish shape. Details as the iliac spine were also vectorized for each *Argyropelecus* genus (Figure 20).

Figure 20: Symbols that were applied to Sternoptychidae. 1: Eye tubular, directed dorsally, 2: Dorsal spines, 3: Caudal fin, 4: Anal fin, 5: Large photophore fin, 6: Iliac spine, 7: Small photophore with black bord, 8: Small photophore without bord, 9: Lateral eyes, 10: Dorsal fin, 11: Valen photophores, 12: Pelvic fin, 13: Special photophore, 14: Pectoral fin.

3.3.1 Genus *Argyropelecus*

For the *Argyropelecus* genus, 6 species were vectorized (Figure 21, 22, 23).

Figure 21: Genus *Argyropelecus*. A1: Outline model for *Argyropelecus affinis*, A2: Vector illustration *Argyropelecus affinis* with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Dorsal shape smooth) B1: Outline model for *Argyropelecus gigas*, B2: Vector illustration *Argyropelecus gigas* with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Diagnostic structures (Dorsal shape irregular).

Argyropelecus olfersi

Argyropelecus acuelatus

Figure 22: Genus *Argyropelecus*. A1: Outline model for *Argyropelecus olfersi*, A2: Vector illustration *Argyropelecus olfersi* with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Same sizes) B1: Outline model for *Argyropelecus acuelatus*, B2: Vector illustration *Argyropelecus acuelatus* with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Different sizes).

Argyropelecus hemigymnus

Argyropelecus sladeni

Figure 23: Genus *Argyropelecus*. A1: Outline model for *Argyropelecus hemigymnus*, A2: Vector illustration *Argyropelecus hemigymnus* with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Serrillate). B1: Outline model for *Argyropelecus sladeni*, B2: Vector illustration *Argyropelecus sladeni* with symbols applied and corrected, B3: Diagnostic structures (Iliac spines: Blunt).

3.3.2 Genus *Polyipnus*

For the *Polyipnus* genus, just 1 specie was vectorized (Figure 24).

Polyipnus polli

Figure 24: Genus *Polyipnus*. A1: Outline model for *Polyipnus polli*, A2: Vector illustration *Polyipnus polli* with symbols applied and corrected, A3: Diagnostic structures (Small dorsal spines).

3.3.3 Genus *Sternoptyx*

For the *Sternoptyx* genus, 2 species were vectorized (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Genus *Sternoptyx*. A1: Outline model for *Sternoptyx diaphana*, A2: Vector illustration *Sternoptyx diaphana* with symbols applied and corrected. B1: Outline model for *Sternoptyx pseudoobscura*, B2: Vector illustration *Sternoptyx pseudoobscura* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.3.4 Genus *Maurolicus*

For the *Maurolicus* genus, 1 species was vectorized (Figure 26).

Maurolicus muelleri

Figure 26: Genus *Maurolicus*. A1: Outline model for *Maurolicus muelleri*, A2: Vector illustration *Maurolicus muelleri* with symbols applied and corrected.

3.3.5 Genus *Valenciennellus*

For the *Valenciennellus* genus, 1 specie was vectorized (Figure 27).

Valenciennellus tripunctulatus

Figure 27: Genus *Valenciennellus*. A1: Outline model for *Valenciennellus tripunctulatus*, A2: Vector illustration *Valenciennellus tripunctulatus* with symbols applied and corrected.

4 Discussion

Understanding how illustrations work in science can not be done in a generalized manner, it must be grounded in the dynamics of a specific discipline (Mishra & Mishra 2009), as it is produced for a specific kind of visual communication in the sciences. This communication can pass from scientist to colleague, teacher to student, or research foundation to layman. The artist must therefore be aware of the viewers level of knowledge and must relate the message in a logical sequence without confusing them with too much or too little information (de Oliveira & Conduru 2004). The artist must be knowledgeable about the subject and draw in a selective and interpretative manner, not photographically recording everything, with the illustration, even being connected to the text, but also using from some autonomy, where details can be removed or highlighted (Julianele 1997). The art must be rendered with scientific accuracy and artistic integrity. In this kind of illustration, learning to draw is learning to see (Wood & McDonnell 1994).

In this context, taxonomy is the area in scientific illustration that more demands accuracy from the artist, as even minimal details can define different species. Significant advances in disseminating taxonomic knowledge are pressing the boundaries of traditional techniques and challenging researchers to upgrade their methodology. Preparation of drawings are the most time-consuming part of taxonomic description. Before the use of desktops for illustrating and publishing, traditional tools like pens, colours and pigments were used for illustrating. Nevertheless, traditional tools are always difficult to learn. It takes years for a person learns using the airbrushes and other tools. It also requires a lot investment in terms of machines, paints etc. During old days, using traditional painting methods were profitable as the illustrators were paid well for their creations at that time. But now, it came down incredibly. In addition, the number of illustrations required per day has become very high. It is not possible for a traditional illustrator to provide more than three illustrations a day using traditional methods. With the coming of modern illustrating methods, new people who are well learnt in computers started giving good illustrations quickly. Thus, illustrators are now forced to use novel techniques for their survival in the illustration arena.

With the development of computer drawing software, the illustration process in taxonomy became much optimized by allowing either the "inking" of pencil sketches after scanning them, or the outlining of necessary details from a digital photograph or image stack (Coleman 2006; Fisher 2010; Tereshkin 2008). Digital drawing techniques that use vector graphics have already been described in literature to support scientists in drawing figures and plates for scientific illustrations (Coleman 2003; Coleman 2009); these techniques use a range of software packages and various hardware devices, such as digitiser boards or digital graphic pens.

The digital illustration brings a lot of functional advantages, since the drawing it is done in digital environment, it will save space and has the possibility of reuse structures already illustrated in other works, which can speed up the process (Coleman 2003). Also, it is possible a countless numbers of copies and adjustments in the artwork, where it can be saved each step for a fully control of the creation process, being also saved in physical supports as DVD/CD and virtual support as Harddrives or updating in internet cloud, which

gives you the guarantee and practicality your work will be always saved and easy to access whatever you go.

When drawing needs to be full-color, with shadings and subtle tint changes (Tereshkin 2008), raster graphic software provides major advantages, as it is primarily dedicated to image creation and processing. For simpler organized line drawings, however, vector graphic suites allow greater freedom bringing a lot advantages in this field, as the parameters of objects are stored and can be later modified, being easy to incorporate new image information from multiple sources (Fisher 2010). This means that moving, scaling, rotating, filling etc. will not degrade the quality of a drawing. Moreover, it is usual to specify the dimensions in device-independent units, which results in the best possible rasterization on raster devices.

This study showed that vectors can also speed up the illustration process in taxonomy, as it is possible to copy and edit structures that appear similar in many species, in this case fish structures as finrays, spines and photophores. Thus, creating groups of structures that will be used across a genera, can save much time. Additionally, being this structures saved as symbols in a library can also reduce file size, reducing the use of memory RAM from computer, optimizing the creation process which can speed the species description process, potentially allowing taxonomists to describe more species annually, as well as producing more accurate, crisper images. Additionally, all the vectors created are compatible to be worked in Adobe Photoshop to make final art, directed to scientific communication. It is easy to export an Illustrator file (EPS or native AI) to Photoshop. This will give more flexibility than simply importing it in Photoshop. If the Illustrator file is built with layers, those can be preserved in the export, as can any live type.

In this work, two families of mesopelagic fishes were illustrated to apply the vector symbols library methodology. Also, for this families, no taxonomical key is available so far for the area they were sampled, thus this work comes to complement the knowledge of this families for the East Atlantic area, which has the higher carency of identification guides (Costello *et al.* 2006). Two digital keys were used for references, the Marine Species Identification Portal (<http://species-identification.org/index.php>) and the FishBase. FishBase is a global species database and a biodiversity information system on all extant fish species of the world, with about 32.000 valid species currently recognized as valid. It contains a wide range of information and data on biology, ecology, chorology, taxonomy, physiology, human uses, illustrations, etc. and aims at being the web global encyclopaedia on fishes. The richness of illustrations is a great advantage for taxonomists, but in terms of illustration, the most used digital identification keys are limited. The Marine Species Identification Portal provides very low resolution images, which it is also not possible to download, and FishBase, where photographs present very low resolution images.

Thus, the possibility to upload vector files of species in this kind of databases should be discussed in terms of Cybertaxonomy. Cybertaxonomy is an integrated way to apply taxonomy using standardized electronic tools and resources, taking advantage of the growing number of online repositories, linked data, and to be easily updatable and data journals can make sharing exceedingly easy (Burguiere *et al.* 2013), as the open-access movement encourages researchers to share primary data (Costello 2009), which could also work encouraging artists to share vector models. Thus, through cyberinfrastructure and the adoption

of digital technologies, cybertaxomy is able to produce results faster and better than ever before (Wheeler 2008; Wheeler 2010). Furthermore, future research programs are enhanced by re-using and re-purposing available data in analyses and syntheses. One of the features of cybertaxonomy are the digital identification keys, which are built to be used on CD-ROM or over the internet. They have some advantage over printed books in the ease of including a rich selection of colour illustrations, in the speed of updating, and in certain advantages of interactive use, which are especially relevant in pedagogical scenarios.

However, they are suitable primarily for indoor workplaces, but usually not practical in the field. With the development of more powerful mobile devices with higher resolution it becomes worthwhile to create digital keys for mobile devices. Such keys must take into account the specific requirements of a small display screen and cumbersome typing to achieve a user-friendly design. In case of vectorial illustrations, it is possible to change line thickness to adapt to any device.

With an increasing number of species described, at daily rate, it will become possible to improve and better test assumptions and models on species diversity, distributions, co-occurrences, and co-varying factors; detect climate change; track species losses or gains; deepen our understanding of interactions among species in ecosystems; improve strategies and priorities for conservation; and predict the expansion or contraction of ranges. Additionally, previous works (Guarino *et al.* 2010) suggests that, in order to raise the interest of non-experts in the identification of species, the learning object must be visually attractive and the learning process must be “blended”: words should be well calibrated with illustrations, concepts must be clear and essential. The quality of the images and their “appeal” are essential, as well as the possibility for users to interact online, to share information and contents with other users and with scientists, to become members of a virtual forum that keeps active thanks to the inputs of a large number of people.

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I Identification keys

Initial note: The species registered for Cape Verde region are in bold letters. The asterisks indicate new records for the area.

I.1 Key to the Cape Verde genera of Myctophidae

1a

Photophores absent. Caudal peduncle with well-developed supra- and infra-caudal glands, bordered by heavy black pigment

Taaningichthys (part 1)

1b

Photophores always present. Caudal peduncle with supra- or infra-caudal glands, or both, or caudal glands absent

2

2a

VLO, SAO3 and Pol close to dorsal contour of body. 2 Prc, with Prc2 above horizontal septum.

Notolychnus

2b

VLO, SAO3 and Pol below or slightly above lateral line, well below dorsal contour of body. 2 or more Prc. Prc2 never above horizontal septum or lateral line.

3

3a

PLO from less than its diameter above to well below level of upper of base of pectoral fin.

4

3b

PLO more than its diameter above to well below level of upper of base of pectoral fin.

8

4a

Mouth sub-terminal. Snout conical and more or less protruding. PLO at or slightly above level of upper end of base of pectoral fin. AO series divided into AOa and AOp. Caudal peduncle markedly slender, its least depth 2,5 or more times in its length.

5

4b

Mouth terminal. Snout not protruding. PLO well below level of upper base of pectoral fin. AO series continuous. Caudal peduncle not markedly slender, its least depth less than 2,5 times in its length

Electrona

5a

Gillrakers absent (reduced to spiny knobs)

Centrobranchus

5b

Gillrakers present.

6

6a

Origin of anal fin under middle of base of dorsal fin. None or only one AOp over base of anal fin. Least depth of caudal peduncle about 2,5 times in its length.

Loweina

6b

Origin of anal fin on or slightly in advance of vertical through base of last dorsal ray. 5 to 7 AOp over base of anal fin. Least depth of caudal peduncle 3,5 or more times in its length.

Gonichthys

7a

PVO2 well above level of upper end of base of pectoral fin. 2 (sometimes 3) Pol, horizontally arranged.

Notoscopelus

7b

PVO2 at or below level of upper end of base of pectoral fin.

9

8a

2 Prc.

10

8b

More than 2 Prc.

14

9a

PVO series horizontal, with PVO1 not more than its own diameter below level of PVO2. VO2 elevated

11

9b

PVO series horizontal, with PVO1 not more than its own diameter below level of PVO2. VO2 series level

12

10a

Prc horizontal or with Prc2 only very slightly raised, lying more than twice its diameter below lateral line. Outer, posterior premaxillary and dentary teeth broad-based and hooked.

Diogenichthys

10b

Prc2 much higher than Prc1, lying at or less than its diameter below lateral line. Outer, posterior premaxillary and dentary teeth small and conical.

Benthosema

11a
2 Pol
Hygophum

11b
1 Pol.
13

12a
SAO strongly angulated, with SAO1 in advance of
(seldom directly over) VO3.
Symbolophorus

12b

SAO in a straight or slightly angulated line. SAO1 behind VO3.

Myctophum

13a

PO1, PVO1 and PVO2 on a straight ascending line. VO1-VO3 on a straight ascending line. 4 Prc.

15

13b

PO1, PVO1 and PVO2 not on a straight ascending line. VO1-VO3 not on a straight ascending line. 3-4 Prc.

16

14a

Dn and Vn present on head. Supra-caudal and infra-caudal glands absent in both sexes.

Diaphus

14b

Dn only present on head. Supra-caudal (males) and infra-caudal (females) luminous glands well developed.

Lobianchia

15a

Supra- and infra-caudal glands large, singular and bordered by heavy black pigment.

17

15b

Supra- and infra-caudal glands consisting of a series of overlapping scale-like or spiny structures, not bordered by heavy black pigment.

18

16a

Origin of dorsal fin behind base of pelvic fin. A large crescent of whitish tissue on posterior half of iris. 1 SAO

Taaningichthys (part 2)

16b

Origin of dorsal fin directly above or somewhat in advance of base of pelvic fin. No large crescent of whitish tissue on posterior half of iris (*Lampadena chavesi* with whitish crescent on dorsal half of iris). 3 SAO.

Lampadena

17a

PO4 not elevated. Luminous scale-like structures mid-ventrally between bases of ventral fin or between bases of pelvic fins and anus.

Ceratoscopelus

17b

PO4 highly elevated. No luminous scale-like structures mid-ventrally between bases of ventral fins or between pelvic fins and anus.

19

18a

Patches of luminous tissue at bases of median and paired fins. 5 VO.

20

18b

No patches of luminous tissue at bases of median and paired fins. Luminous tissue (other than photophores) restricted to supra- and infra-caudal glands and sometimes to base of adipose fin. 4 VO (rarely 5).

Lampanyctus

19a

3 Prc only. Crescent of whitish tissue on posterior half of iris. Posterodorsal margin of operculum sharply pointed and markedly anteriorly concave.

Bolinichthys

19b

4 (sometimes more) Prc. No crescent of whitish tissue on posterior half of iris. Posterodorsal margin of operculum broadly rounded and only very slightly anteriorly concave.

Lepidophanes

20a

Body profile appearing pinched. Short (never reaching far beyond pelvic fin base), rudimentary, or no pectoral fins with narrow base always equal to or shorter than distance between lower orbital margin and toothed margin of upper jaw in the adult. Gillrakers always less than 21.

Nannobranchium

20b

Body profile slightly elongated, not appearing pinched. Pectoral fins developed, longer than distance between lower orbital margin and toothed margin of upper jaw in the adult. *L. macdonaldi* is the only Atlantic species with short pectoral fins, but 21 or more gillrakers).

Lampanyctus

I.1.1 *Benthosema* Goode & Bean, 1896

1a

So absent. Gillrakers 5(6) + 1 + 12 (11-13), total 18 (17-20). SAO weakly angulated, forming even curve with concavity directed antero-ventrally. VLO below line PLO-SA01.

B. glaciale* (Reinhardt, 1837)

1b

So present. Gillrakers 3 + 1 + 10 (9, rarely 11), total 14 (13, rarely 15). SAO angulated. VLO above the line PLO-SA01.

B. suborbitale (Gilbert, 1913)

I.1.2 *Bolinichthys* Paxton, 1972

1a

VLO at about lateral line. Luminous scale at pelvic fin base present. 3 small post-ocular photophores present:

2

1b

VLO 2-5 photophore diameters below lateral line. Luminous scale at pelvic fin base absent. Small post-ocular photophores absent.

B. supralateralis (Parr, 1928)

2a

Preopercle with strongly developed, anteriorly recurved spine at posteroventral margin; luminous patch at PVO1 present. Gillrakers 6 (5-7) + 1 + 13-14 (11-16), total 20-21 (18- 23)

B. photothorax (Parr, 1928)

2b

Preopercle with only small protuberance at posteroventral margin. Luminous patch at PVO1 absent. Gillrakers 4 (rarely 3 or 5) + 1 + 11 (10-12), total 16 (15-17, rarely 18)

*B. indicus** (Nafpaktitis & Nafpaktitis, 1969)

I.1.3 *Centrobranchus* Fowler, 1904

1a

SAO1 above VO4 or behind vertical through this photophore. AO 6-7 (5-8) + 10-11 (7-12), total 17 (15-19).

C. andreae (Lütken, 1892)

1b

SAO1 above VO2-VO3 interspace. AO 5-6 (4-7) + 9-10 (8-11), total 14-16 (13-17).

C. nigroocellatus (Günther, 1837)

I.1.4 *Ceratoscopelus* Günther, 1864

1a

Supra-orbital spine presente. No median series of luminous scale-like structures between bases of pelvic fins and the anus. Gillrakers total 19 (18-21, rarely 17 or 22). Tips of caudal rays pigmented.

C. maderensis (Lowe, 1839)

1b

Supra-orbital spine absent. A median series of luminous scale-like structures between the bases of pelvic fins and the anus present. Gillrakers total 14 (13-15, rarely 16). Tips of caudal rays not pigmented.

C. warmingii (Lütken, 1892)

I.1.5 *Diaphus* Eigenmann & Eigenmann, 1890

1a

So always present, on ventral orbital margin, completely separated from Vn or connected with latter by a strand of dark tissue of varied breadth. Inner series of teeth on posterior part of premaxillary always with broad bases and strongly recurved. Vomer naked or with very few, scattered minute teeth:

2

1b

So absent. Inner series of teeth on posterior part of premaxillary of various sizes, sometimes distinctly recurved. Vomer with a small, round or oval patch of teeth on each side:

8

2a

Dn very small, inconspicuous, directed laterally, shallowly embedded and almost completely fused with much larger, upward spreading Vn. A narrow band of dark tissue extending along ventral border of eye connects the Vn with the small So, the latter located somewhat behind vertical through center of lens. Diameter of eye more than 2 times in length of upper jaw. Upper jaw extending about one time the diameter of eye behind vertical through posterior border of orbit.

D. vanhoeffeni Brauer, 1906

2b

Dn well defined, round, equal in size to or somewhat smaller than nasal rosette, directed forward and set in deep, cut-shaped recess above nasal apparatus. Vn on ventral orbital margin, completely and widely separated from Dn. Diameter of eye 2 times in length of upper jaw or less. Upper jaw extending about one half the diameter of eye behind vertical through posterior margin of orbit :

3

3a

So behind vertical through posterior margin of pupil, occupying the anteroventral and most of ventral orbital margin. No luminous scale at PLO.

D. brachycephalus Täning, 1928

3b

So in advance of vertical through posterior margin of pupil. Vn elongate but shorter than horizontal diameter of pupil, or small, rounded, about equal in size to So. A luminous scale at PLO, this sometimes poorly defined or rubbed off :

4

4a

Vn and So about equal in size, roundish or oval, small, 1/3 to 1/2 the size of a general body photophore and widely separated from each other. Body photophores placed low, very large in size and separated by narrow spaces; spaces between AO equal to about 1/2 the diameter of a photophore. AOa1 not raised. Very large luminous scale at PLO:

D. anderseni Tåning, 1932

4b

Vn elongate, much larger than roundish or oval So, the 2 organs close to each other, sometimes confluent. Body photophores of moderate size, those of AO series separated by spaces greater than 1/2 the diameter of a photophore:

5

5a

AOp 5 or more, usually 6, continuous or nearly so with Prc. Prc1-Prc3 distance larger than AOp-Prc interspace. Gillrakers 6 (7) + 1 + 13-14, total 20-22.

D. subtilis Nafpaktitis, 1968

5b

AOp 5 or less, usually 4, well separated from Prc. Prc1-Prc3 distance equal to or usually smaller than AOp-Prc interspace:

6

6a

AOa 6, seldom 5 or 7. AOa1 abruptly elevated, its ventral margin above a line through dorsal margins of next 2 photophores of same series. SAO on a straight or very slightly angulated line. A large luminous scale at PLO. Gillrakers 7-8 + 1 + 14-16, total 22-24 (25).

*D. rafinesquii** (Cocco, 1838)

6b

AOa 5, seldom 6. AOa1 in a straight line with next 2 photophores of same series or raised forming with next 2 or 3 photophores of this series a gentle curve. SAO on a straight or distinctly angular line. Small luminous scale at PLO, often poorly defined or rubbed off. Gillrakers 15-20 :

7

7a

Distance between PLO and lateral line 1,5 times as great as that between upper end of base of pectoral fin or less. SAO forming a distinctly angular line, SAO3 1- 1,5 times its own diameter below lateral line. Pol about its own diameter below lateral line. SL length more than 8 times caudal peduncle depth. Postero-dorsal opercular margin angular. Gillrakers 4-5 + 1 + 11 (10- 12), total 16 (15-18).

D. mollis Tåning, 1928

7b

Distance between PLO and lateral line 2-2.5 times as great as that between PLO and upper end of base of pectoral fin. SAO in a straight or slightly angular line. SAO3 2-2.5 times its own diameter below lateral line. Pol about twice its own diameter below lateral line. SL length 8 times caudal peduncle depth or less. Postero-dorsal opercular margin evenly rounded. Gillrakers 5-6 + 1 + 12-13 (11), total 18-20.

D. holti Tåning, 1918

8a

Dn small, thin, rather poorly defined (usually larger and better defined in adult males), shallowly embedded and directed laterally. Vn equally small, completely separated from Dn, located at ventral orbital margin, or somewhat larger and located at anteroventral aspect of orbit and connected with Dn by a narrow streak of luminous tissue in between eye and nasal apparatus :

9

8b

Dn well defined, in more or less deep recess above nasal apparatus and directed forward. Vn restricted to anteroventral or ventral aspect of orbit, or spreading along anterior orbital margin, often reaching the Dn :

11

9a

Small, round or oval Vn, half the size of a general body photophore, completely separated from Dn, located at the ventral orbital margin on or slightly in advance of vertical through anterior margin of pupil. PLO in advance of vertical through upper end of base of pectoral fin and very high, 1-2 times its own diameter below lateral line. SAO angular, SAO3 and Pol at lateral line. AOa1 not elevated.

D. dumerilii (Bleeker, 1856)

9b

Vn at anteroventral aspect of orbit, somewhat larger than Dn and connected with it by a thin streak of luminous tissue extending between eye and nasal apparatus. PLO behind vertical through upper end of base of pectoral fin. SAO series not or slightly angular. AOa1 abruptly elevated, well above next 2-3 photophores of same series :

10

10a

PLO nearer to lateral line than to base of pectoral fin. VLO midway between lateral line and base of ventral fin. SAO3 and Pol in contact with lateral line. First AOp entirely behind end of base of anal fin. Gillrakers 7 (rarely 6 or 8) + 1 + 13-14 (rarely 12 or 15), total 21-22 (rarely 20 or 23).

D. garmani Gilbert, 1906

10b

PLO nearer to base of pectoral fin than to lateral line. VLO nearer to lateral line than to base of ventral fin. SAO3 and Pol 1-1,5 times their diameters below lateral line. First AOp over base of anal fin. Gillrakers 4 + 1 + 9 (8), total 14 (13).

D. problematicus Parr, 1928

11a

Dn smaller than nasal rosette. Vn extending upward to or beyond level of Dn or restricted below nostril but connected with Dn by a strand of dark tissue extending along anterior orbital margin
:

12

11b

Dn equal in size to or larger than nasal rosette, round or rectangular, often reaching medial ethmoid crest. Vn also very large, spreading along entire area entire in front, coming in contact with Dn, its ventral portion extending at least a short distance along ventral orbital margin. Ant photophore may or may not be present :

17

12a

Vn extending dorsally between eye and nasal apparatus, reaching Dn:

13

12b

Vn not spreading dorsally between lower margin of nasal apparatus:

14

13a

Vn not extending along ventral orbital margin, its posterior end barely reaching vertical through anterior margin of pupil. Elongate luminous organ along dorsal margin of orbit absent. Anterior end of Supraorbital frontal ridge produced into a forward directed spine – often broken in preserved specimens. PLO nearer to base of pectoral fin than to lateral line. SAO3 and Pol in contact with lateral line.

D. splendidus (Brauer, 1904)

13b

Vn extending along ventral orbital margin, its posterior end on or behind vertical through center of lens. Luminous organ extending along entire or nearly entire dorsal orbital margin. Anterior end of supraorbital frontal ridge not produced into a spine. PLO midway between base of pectoral fin and lateral line or somewhat higher. SAO3 and Pol not in contact with lateral line.

D. adenomus Gilbert, 1905

14a

SAO1 above level of VO5. Upper jaw extending more than one time the diameter of eye behind vertical through posterior margin of orbit. Ventral fins somewhat reaching origin of anal fin:

15

14b

SAO1 on same level with VO5. Upper jaw extending more than one time the diameter of eye behind vertical through posterior margin of orbit. Ventral fins extending beyond origin of anal fin:

16

15a

Body photophores of moderate size, those of AOp series separated by spaces larger than 1/2 the diameter of a photophore. VLO midway between lateral line and base of ventral fin or somewhat higher. Gillrakers 6-7 + 1 + 13-14, total 20-22

D. taaningi Norman, 1930

15b

Body photophores large, those of AOp series separated by spaces equal to 1/2 the diameter of a photophore or less. VLO nearer to base of ventral fin than to lateral line. Gillrakers 5 + 1 + 12.

D. bertelseni Nafpaktitis, 1968

16a

Vn very long, extending along most of ventral border of eye, its dorsal margin with small, round, bud-like projections. Dorsal and anal fins overlapping.

D. luetkeni (Brauer, 1904)

16b

Vn roundish or oval, located on ventral orbital margin, about under center margin of pupil. Dorsal and anal fins not overlapping .

D. termophilus Tåning, 1928

17a

Ant absent :

18

17b

Ant present:

20

18a

Dorsal finrays 13-15. Anal finrays 13-14. HL 3-5 times or more larger than eye diameter. Upper jaw 2 times or less larger than eye diameter. Body photophores of average size:

19

18b

Dorsal finrays 17. Anal finrays 17-18. HL 3-5 times or more larger than eye diameter. Upper jaw 2,5 times or more larger than eye diameter. Body photophores noticeably small.

D. lucidus (Goode & Bean, 1896)

19a

Head as deep as it is long or very nearly so. Upper jaw extending 1/2 the diameter of eye or less behind vertical through posterior margin of orbit.

D. minax Nafpaktitis, 1968

19b

Head considerably longer than it is deep. Upper jaw extending more than 1/2 the diameter of eye behind through posterior margin of orbit. Dn roughly rectangular, much larger than nasal rosette.

D. roei Nafpaktitis, 1974

20a

Ventral portion of Vn not reaching vertical through anterior margin of pupil. Head much longer than deep. Body photophores of average size :

21

20b

Vn extending along ventral orbital margin to somewhat behind vertical through center of pupil. Head nearly as deep as it is long. Body photophores noticeably small.

D. metopoclampus (Cocco, 1829)

21a

Dn hardly extending higher than level of dorsal margin of eye. PLO midway between lateral line and base of pectoral fin or higher. SAO3 and Pol in contact with, or less than their diameter below, lateral line :

22

21b

Dn extending higher than level of dorsal margin of eye. PLO nearer to pectoral base than to lateral line. SAO3 and Pol 1,5-3 times their diameter below lateral line. Gillrakers 6-7 + 1 + 13 (14), total 20-21 (22).

D. effulgens (Goode & Bean, 1896)

22a

Vn not spreading behind nasal apparatus. Diameter of eye less than 10% of SL. Lower jaw with inner series of markedly large, widely but more or less regularly spaced teeth. Gillrakers 5 (6) + 1 + 11-12, total 17-18 (19).

D. fragilis Tåning, 1928

22b

Vn spreading behind nasal apparatus, reaching the medial ethmoid crest. Diameter of eye more than 10% of SL. No markedly enlarged teeth on lower jaw. Gillrakers 9-10 + 1 + 16-17 (18), total 26-28 (29).

D. perspicillatus (Ogilby, 1898)

I.1.6 *Diogenichthys* Bolin, 1939

3 species, the only one present in area being *Diogenichthys atlanticus* (Tåning, 1928)

I.1.7 *Electrona* Goode & Bean, 1896

5 species, the only one present in area being *Electrona risso* (Cocco, 1829)

I.1.8 *Gonichthys* Gistel, 1850

4 species, the only one present in area being *Gonichthys cocco* (Cocco, 1829)

I.1.9 *Hygophum* Bolin, 1939

1a

Last AOa, Pol1 and Pol2 on a straight line or, at most, Pol1 slightly in advance of, but in contact with, a straight line through anterior margins of last AOa and Pol2, always behind vertical through center of last AOa:

2

1b

Last AOa, Pol1 and Pol2 not on a straight line. Pol1 distinctly in advance of a straight line through anterior margins of last AOa and Pol2 on or in front of vertical through center of last AOa :

3

2a

Prc2 low in position. Prc1-Prc2 interspace equal to, or smaller than, distance between Prc2 and lateral line. Distance between posterior end of base of dorsal fin and Prc2 smaller than distance between tip of snout and base of ventral fins.

H. benoiti (Cocco, 1838)

2b

Prc2 high in position. Prc1-Prc2 interspace much greater than distance between Prc2 and lateral line. Distance between posterior end of base of dorsal fin and Prc2 greater than distance between tip of snout and base of ventral fins.

H. reinhardtii (Lütken, 1892)

3a

VLO in contact with, or less than its diameter below lateral line. SAO1 in front of, rarely on, vertical through center of VO2

H. hygomii (Lütken, 1892)

3b

VLO midway between base of ventral fin and lateral line, or somewhat higher. SAO1 well behind VO2 :

4

4a

SAO1 in front of vertical through center of VO3, VO4, SAO2 and SAO3 on a straight line. Pectoral fins extending beyond AOa1. Gillrakers 5 (4) + 1 + 14 (13-15), total 19-20. Supra-caudal luminous gland of 5-7, usually 6, distinct scale-like structures.

H. macrochir (Günther, 1864)

4b

SAO1 behind ,rarely on, vertical through center of VO3. A Straight line through SAO2 and SAO3 passing behind VO4. Pectoral fins not reaching AOa1. Gillrakers 4 + 1 + 12 (11-13), total 17 (16-18). Supra-caudal luminous gland with no distinct scale-like structures.

H. taaningi Bekker, 1965

I.1.10 *Lampadena* Goode & Bean, 1896

1a

PO4 abruptly and highly elevated, about over PO3.

L. luminosa (Garman, 1899)

1b

None of the PO abruptly and highly elevated :

2

2a

VO plus SAO 5-6. AOa 3-4. Pol more than its diameter below lateral line. Gillrakers 5 + 1 + 11 (10-12), total 17 (16-18).

L. anomala Parr, 1928

2b

VO plus SAO 7-9. AOa 5-7. Pol its diameter or less below lateral line :

3

3a

Prc1-Prc2 interspace much shorter than 3 times the diameter of a photophore of this series. Last 2 (sometimes 3) AOa behind base of anal fin. Infra-caudal luminous gland very long, reaching AOa series, its length more than 14% of SL. Crescent of whitish tissue on dorsal half of iris.

L. chavesi Collett, 1905

3b

Prc1-Prc2 interspace much shorter than 3 times the diameter of a photophore of this series. No AOa behind base of anal fin. Length of infra-caudal luminous gland less than 14% of SL, not reaching AOa series. No crescent of whitish tissue on dorsal half of iris :

4

4a

Gillrakers 3-5 + 1 + 8-10. Supra-caudal luminous gland equal in length to, or somewhat longer than, infra-caudal gland. Medial and posterior mesopterygoid teeth markedly enlarged.

L. urophaos atlantica Maul, 1969

4b

Gillrakers 6-8 + 1 + 8-10. Supra-caudal luminous gland shorter than infra-caudal gland. Mesopterygoid teeth uniformly small :

5

5a

Distance between end of base of anal fin and anterior margin of infra-caudal gland equal to, or greater than, length of this gland. Gillrakers 19-22.

L. speculigera, Goode & Bean, 1896

5b

Distance between end of base of anal fin and anterior margin of infra-caudal gland much less (though more than 1/3) than length of this gland. Gillrakers 22-26.

L. pontifex Krefft, 1970

I.1.11 *Lampanyctus* Bonaparte, 1840

1a

Branchiostegal membrane with minute serial photophores between branchiostegal rays. Secondary photophores on head, body and fins.

2

1b

Branchiostegal membrane without minute serial photophores between branchiostegal rays. No secondary photophores on head, body and fins

3

2a

Luminous gland at origin of adipose fin absent. VLO midway between lateral line and ventral base.

L. pusillus (Johnson, 1890)

2b

Luminous gland at origin of adipose fin present.
VLO at or just below lateral line.

L. alatus Goode & Bean, 1896

3a

1 or more photophores on cheek :

4

3b

No photophores on cheek :

7

4a

Luminous gland at adipose fin origin absent

L. photonotus Parr, 1928

4b

Luminous gland present at adipose fin origin or just in front of adipose fin :

5

5a

Total number of gillrakers on first gill arch 21-26 :

L. macdonaldi (Goode & Bean, 1896)

5b

Total number of gillrakers on first gill arch 15-18 :

6

6a

AOa 9 (8-10), with AOa1 and/or AOa2 abruptly depressed, line passing through AOa1-AOa2 below AOa3. Gillrakers 4 + 1 + 10 (rarely 9 or 11), total 15 (rarely 14 or 16).

*L. intricarius** (Tåning, 1928)

6b

AOa 6 (7), with AOa1, AOa2 not abruptly depressed, line passing through AOa1-AOa2 above AOa3. Gillrakers 5 (rarely 4) + 1 + 11 (10-12), total 17 (16-18).

*L. crocodilus** (Risso, 1810)

7a

SAO1 behind VO3. Prc separate from AOp.
Prc2-4 in a straight line.

L. nobilis Tåning, 1928

7b

SAO1 in front of, seldom directly over, VO3. Prc
continuous with AOp. Prc2-4 not in a straight line :

12

12a

Pectoral finrays 15-17. AO 15-16. Prc3 usually
higher than Prc1.

L. festivus Tåning, 1928

12b

Pectoral finrays 13-14. AO 12-13. Prc3 usually at
level of Prc1

L. tenuiformis (Brauer, 1906)

L. vadulus Hully, 1981 registered in area (Hartel, 2002)
But taxonomic information unknown.

I.1.12 *Lepidophanes* Fraser-Brunner, 1949

1a

Gillrakers 3 + 1 + 8 (rarely 7), total 12 (rarely 11).
Small round photophores on midline between
posterior end of dorsal fin and origin of adipose
fin. Luminous tissue at origin of ventral fin and
below pectoral fin.

L. gaussi (Brauer, 1906)

1b

Gillrakers 4 + 1 + 9 (rarely 8 or 10), total 14 (rarely
13 or 15). No small photophores on midline
between posterior end of dorsal fin and origin of
adipose fin. No luminous tissue at ventral base or
below pectoral fin.

L. guentheri (Goode & Bean, 1896)

I.1.13 *Lobianchia* Gatti, 1903

1a

Distance between Pol and base of anal fin or ventral contour of caudal peduncle 2-2,5 times as great as distance between Pol and lateral line. SAO forming gentle arc, convexity directed postero-ventrally. Prc4 separated from Prc3 by a greatly enlarged interspace, lying at base of middle caudal rays. Distance between Prc4 and Prc3 equal to or usually greater than distance between Prc1 and Prc3.

L. dofleini, (Zugmayer, 1911)

1b

Pol midway between lateral line and base of anal fin or lower. SAO on a straight or slightly curved line, convexity directed antero-ventrally. Prc evenly spaced, sometimes Prc4 somewhat displaced posteriorly. Distance between Prc4 and Prc3 always smaller than the distance between Prc1 and Prc3.

L. gemellarii (Cocco, 1838)

I.1.14 *Loweina* Fowler, 1925

1a

2 SAO photophores. 4 VO photophores. Gillrakers
2 + 1 + 5-6, total 8-9

L. rara (Lütken, 1892)

1b

3 SAO photophores. 2 VO photophores, at positions corresponding to VO1 and VO4. Gillrakers 3 + 1 + 8-9 (7-10), total 12-13 (11-14)

L. interrupta (Tåning, 1928)

I.1.15 *Myctophum* Rafinesque, 1810

1a

AOp 9 (8), 3-4 over base of anal fin.

M. punctatum Rafinesque, 1810

1b

AOp 7 or fewer, 1 or none over base of anal fin :

2

2a

SAO in a distinctly curved line. Gillrakers 14-16.

M. asperum Richardson, 1845

2b

SAO in a straight or very nearly straight line. Gillrakers 18 or more :

3

3a

AO 12-15. Pectoral finrays 13-14. Gillrakers 18-22

:

4

3b

AO 9-12. Pectoral 16-18. Gillrakers 22-25 :

5

4a

Posterodorsal opercular margin sharply angular.
Scales cycloid

M. nitidulum Garman, 1899

4b

Posterodorsal opercular margin evenly rounded.
Scales ctenoid.

M. affine (Lütken, 1892)

5a

Body short and deep (body depth 3-3,3 times of SL). Head nearly as deep as it is long. Upper posterior opercular margin smooth. Scales strongly ctenoid.

M. selenops Tåning, 1928

5b

Body slender. Head considerably slender longer than deep. Upper posterior opercular margin serrated. Scales cycloid.

M. obtusirostre Tåning, 1928

I.1.16 *Nannobrachium* Günther, 1887

1a

Pectoral fins present :

2

1b

Pectoral fins absent:

6

2a

VO2 raised and forward to a position above VO1.

N. isaacsi (Wisner, 1974)

2b

VO2 not, or only slightly, raised and in normal position, approximately between VO1 and VO3:

3

3a

Supra- and infra-caudal glands bordered by black pigment. SAO1 over VO3-4 interspace. Prc3 on vertical midway between Prc2 and Prc4 :

4

3b

Supra- and infra-caudal glands not bordered by black pigment. SAO1 over VO2-3 interspace. Prc3 directly under Prc4 :

5

4a

Length of caudal peduncle shorter than, or equal to, upper jaw length. Prc3 on line connecting Prc2 and Prc4. Prc continuous with AOp. AO 5-6 + 5-6, total 10-11. Anal finrays 18-19 (17-20)

N. cuprarium (Tåning, 1928)

4b

Length of caudal peduncle longer than upper jaw length. Prc3 below line connecting Prc2 and Prc4. Prc not usually continuous with AOp. AO 7-9 + 6-9, total 14-17. Anal finrays 20-21 (19-23)

N. lineatum (Tåning, 1928)

5a

AO 6-7 (5-9) + 7-8 (6-9), total 13-15 (12). Lateral line organs 36-39. Vertebrae 16 (15) + 21-22 (20-23), total 37-38 (36-39). Anal finrays 19 (17-21)

N. atrum (Tåning, 1928)

5b

AO 5 (4-6) + 5-6 (7), total 10-11 (9-13). Lateral line organs 29-34. Vertebrae 15 (14-16) + 18-20 (17-21), total 33-35 (32-37). Anal finrays 16-17 (14-18)

N. nigrum Günther, 1887

N. niger (Hanel et al. 2010)

1 specimen registered in area, but usual distribution Indic and Pacific Oceans

I.1.17 *Notolychnus* Fraser-Brunner, 1949

1 species only, present in area: ***Notolychnus valvidiae* (Brauer, 1904)**

I.1.18 *Notoscopelus* Günther, 1864

1a

Gillrakers on first arch 4 + 1 + 9 (rarely 8 or 10),
total 14 (rarely 13 or 15)

N. caudispinosus (Johnson, 1863)

1b

Gillrakers on first arch more than 18:

2

2a

Gillrakers 26 or more:

3

2b

Gillrakers 25 or fewer :

4

3a

Dorsal finrays 22 (21). Gillrakers 8 + 1 + 17 (18), total 26 (27). Adult males with supra-caudal luminous gland but no luminous tissue on cheeks or above eyes.

N. kroeyerii (Malm, 1861)

3b

Dorsal finrays 23-26. Gillrakers 8 + 1 + 17 (18), total 26 (27). Adult males with supra-caudal luminous tissue on cheeks and above eyes, but no supra-caudal luminous gland.

N. bolini Nafpaktitis, 1975

Superior latitudes, but present for taxonomic purposes.

4a

Gillrakers 19-23. AO photophores 12-14

N. resplendens (Richardson, 1845)

4b

Gillrakers 23-25. AO photophores 15-17

N. elongatus (Costa, 184)

I.1.19 *Symbolophorus* Bolin & Wisner, 1959

1a

SAO1 directly above VO3. VO4-SAO2-SAO3 forming a straight line.

S. rufinus (Tåning, 1928)

1b

SAO1 directly above VO2 or slightly anterior or posteriorly displaced. VO4-SAO2-SAO3 not forming a straight line :

2

2a

Anal finray reaching 4 (3, almost 5) first AOp. Prc very close to end of caudal peduncle, nearly reaching it.

S. barnardi (Tåning, 1932)

2b

Anal finray reaching 3 first AOp. Prc about interspace between photophores of the series separated from end of caudal peduncle

S. veranyi (Moreau, 1888)

I.1.20 *Taaningichthys* Bolin, 1959

1a

Body photophores absent

T. paurolychnus Davy, 1972

1b

Body photophores present :

2

2a

VO photophores 8-10. AO photophores 5-7 + 4-6, total 9-13. Pol on or anterior to vertical through origin of adipose fin. Prc1-Prc2 interspace equal to or greater than 2 photophore diameters.

T. minimus (Tåning, 1928)

2b

VO photophores 3-5. AO photophores 1-4 + 1-2, total 2-5. Pol well behind vertical through origin of adipose fin. Prc1-Prc2 interspace equal to or greater than 1 photophore diameter

T. bathyphilus (Tåning, 1928)

I.2 Key to the Cape Verde genera of Sternoptychidae

1a

- Body laterally compressed, deep, SL 0,8-2,0 times greater than greatest body depth (juveniles and adults).
- Exposed dorsal blade well to moderately developed.
- Abdominal keel well defined.
- Post-abdominal (iliac) spines well to moderately developed.

2

1b

- Body fusiform, SL 3,7-7,7 times greater than greatest body depth.
- Dorsal blade
- Post abdominal (iliac) spines absent.
- Abdominal keel absent or inconspicuous :

4

2a

- Dorsal blade of several spines.
- Eyes tubular, directed dorsally.

Argyropelecus

3

- Dorsal blade of 1 or 2 spines.
- Eyes normal, directed laterally.
- PV = 10

3a

- Dorsal blade of single spine with serrate anterior projection.
- Photophores: BR 3. IP 5. ORB ventral to eye, unpigmented and externally indistinct, directed into mouth:

Sternoptyx

3b

- Dorsal blade reduced, of 2 fused pterygiophores.
- Photophores: BR 6, IP 6, ORB pigmented, anterior to and directed into eye

Polyipnus

4a

- Photophores: AC in 3-6 groups, each of 2-4 photophores. IP in 2 groups, of 3-4 photophores.
- Gillrakers on first arch 12 (13) + 2-3 (4), total 14-15 (16)

Valenciennellus

4b

- AC with 2-3 groups of 5 or more photophores. IP in a single group of 6 (rarely 7) photophores. Gillrakers on first arch 11-22 + 3-8, total 15-30

5

5a

- Dorsal fin origin behind middle of body length.
- Anal fin not divided into 2 distinctly separated ray groups by AC group.
- SO present. OP3 single, directed ventrally.

Maurolicus

5b

- Dorsal fin origin about or anterior to middle of body length.
- Anal fin divided into 2 distinct ray groups by AC photophores.
- Photophores: SO absent. OP3 greatly enlarged, double, with dorsal and ventral apertures

6

6a

- VAV and anterior AC form continuous photophore group, extending over anterior anal rays.
- First anal finray group of 11 (rarely 10) -15 rays.
- Dorsal adipose fin present.

Argyripnus

6b

- VAV separated from AC photophores.
- No photophores over anterior few anal rays.
- First anal finray group 8-10 rays.
- No dorsal adipose fin.

Sonoda

Key to the Cape Verde species of *Argyripnus* Gilbert & Kramer, 1897

7 species, 1 in area ***Argyripnus atlanticus* Maul, 1952**

Key to the Cape Verde species of *Argyropelecus* Gilbert & Kramer, 1897

1a

- VAV, AC1 and AC2 groups well separated, the photophores of each sharing a common photogenic mass.
- VAV, AC1 and AC2 elevated relatively to posterior 6 AOa.
- Anal finrays in 2 distinct groups separated by central AC1 photophores:

2

2a

- Single posteriorly directed post-abdominal spine with serrated edges and bearing small dorso-posterior spine.
- Posterior pair of fused dorsal blade spines with hooks forming barbs.
- Dorsal finrays 8. Anal finrays 6 + 5:

***A. hemigymnus* Cocco, 1829**

- 2b 2 separated post-abdominal spines, one directed antero-ventrally, other postero-ventrally.
- Posterior dorsal blade spines without hooks. Dorsal finrays 9 (10). Anal finrays 7 + 5:

3

- 3a Upper preopercular spine long, extending well beyond posterior edge of preopercle.
- Anteroventrally directed post-abdominal spine blunt, progressively less so in individuals under about 15 mm SL.
- Median superficial caudal chromatophores dorsal to AC2 in juveniles over about 11 mm SL

A. sladeni Regan, 1908

- 3b Upper preopercular spine short, extending little, if at all, beyond posterior edge of preopercle. Antero-ventrally directed post-abdominal spine pointed.
- Enlarged caniniform teeth in lower jaw.
- No median superficial caudal chromatophores dorsal to AC2 in juveniles under 20 mm SL:

4

- 4a Postero-ventrally directed post-abdominal spine longer, markedly larger, than anteroventral one (may be equal in metamorphic post-larvae).
- Anterior margin of posteriormost ventral keel scale curving markedly forwards (metamorphic post-larvae excluded). Spines present under VAV (over about 35 mm SL), between anal finrays (over about 23 mm SL), anteriorly to AC2 photophores (over about 23 mm SL), and ventral to anterior 3 AC2 photophores (over about 35 mm SL):

A. aculeatus Valenciennes, 1849

- 4b Post-abdominal spines equal in size and length.
- Anterior margin of posteriormost ventral keel scale almost vertical.
- No spines present under VAV, between anal finrays, anteriorly to AC2 or ventral to anterior AC2 photophores:

A. offersii (Cuvier, 1828)

- 5a Body profile with fleshy elevation between third and fourth dorsal blade spines and raised markedly posterior to blade (fishes over 20 mm SL).
- Post-orbital spine prominent in adults.
- Snout profile angular.
- In fishes 14-25 mm SL photogenic connection between second and third AC1 photophores very constricted:

A. gigas Norman, 1930

- 5b Body profile ventral to dorsal blade smooth and not raised markedly posterior to blade.
- Post-orbital spine absent. Snout profile smooth.
- In fishes 14-25 mm SL photogenic connection between second and third AC1 photophores substantial, only slightly constricted:

A. affinis Garman, 1899

Key to the Cape Verde species of *Maurolicus* Cocco, 1838

- 1a Gillrakers 22-24 (21-26):

M. weitzmani Parin & Kobylansky, 1993

-
- 1b Gillrakers 27-31:

M. muelleri (Gmelin, 1788)

Key to the Cape Verde species of *Polyipnus* Günther, 1887

32 species, 1 present in area: *Polyipnus polli* Schultz, 1961

Key to the Cape Verde species of *Sternoptyx* Hermann, 1781

- 1a Supra-anal photophore distinctly elevated to the mid-distance between anteroventral margin of AC1 and trunk midline or higher:

S. pseudobscura Baird, 1971

- 1b Supra-anal photophore slightly elevated, closer to anteroventral margin of AC series than to trunk midline:

2

- 2a Body height equal to body length. Dorsal finrays 11-12:

S. pseudodiaphana Baird, 1971

* Not confirmed in area, present for taxonomic purposes

- 2b Body height much larger than body length. Dorsal finrays 9-11:

S. diaphana Hermann, 1781

II Final art

The final art was all based on the previous vectorial illustrations, being the Adobe Photoshop the software used to create and edit the images. The files used were exported from Adobe Illustrator in vector format, that is also compatible with Adobe Photoshop in your basic functions. For each species, the first layer was the vector exported, being the second layer consisted in the base colors and light values. Separated layers were created for each body structures (eyes, finrays and photophores). The final layer was for textures and highlights.

This kind of illustration can be more appealing to a less specialized public, as they do not focus necessarily on taxonomical descriptions, being the colors and shades more relevant to create a more realistic animal that is not normally seem by the general public. Thus final art in Adobe Photoshop it is always an option that can be integrated to vectorial illustration, helping to disseminate scientific information across several kinds of readers.

The examples below of final art for the family Myctophidae (Figure 28) and Sternoptychidae (Figure 29).

Figure 28: Example of final art in Adobe Photoshop for the family Myctophidae. A:*Benthosema glaciale*, B:*Benthosema suborbitale*, C:*Lampanictus intricarius*, D:*Diaphus lucidus*, E:*Nannobranchium atrium*, F:*Symbolophorus* sp., G:*Myctophum* sp. H:*Lobianchia dofleini*, I:*Diogenichthys atlanticus*, J:*Lampanictus nobilis*, L:*Lepidophanes guentheri*, M:*Lampanictus alatus*, N:*Hygophum taaningi*, O:*Bolinichthys photothorax*, P:*Hygophum reinhardti*, Q:*Lampanictus crocodilus*.

Figure 29: Example of final art in Adobe Photoshop for the family Sternoptychidae. A: *Argyrolepecus aculeatus*, B: *Argyrolepecus sladeni*, C: *Argyrolepecus affinis*, D: *Argyrolepecus gigas*, E: *Argyrolepecus hemigymnus*, F: *Argyrolepecus olfersi*, G: *Sternoptyx diaphana*, H: *Sternoptyx pseudoobscura*, I: *Polyipnus polli*, J: *Valenciennellus tripunctulatus*, L: *Maurolicus muelleri*.